

Rhythm alternation using interval sets

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Abstract

Rhythm is at the forefront of musical experience in electronic dance music. The construction of rhythmic patterns and the production of appealing rhythmic timelines is both a logical and creative process and some of these process can be computationally modeled using algorithms. We research an algorithmic method to provide variations of a given rhythmic pattern. This original *seed* pattern is recognized to be important because it is favored either by the electronic artist or in world history. In order to achieve this result, we conduct a multiset permutation of the beat intervals in the original rhythm to generate a class of related rhythms. We then evaluate this set based on *similarity*, *continuation* and *interestingness* ratings and organize them based on said variables to aid the usage of these patterns in the workflow of the electronic artist.

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1 Introduction

Electronic music production is a fast growing and exciting frontier in the field of contemporary music. While the emergence of electronic music into popular culture dates back to the 1970s, the fast growing pace of computer technology has pushed electronic music further into mainstream culture, with new tools and products being released into a growing market and community of electronic music producers and DJs. The sound system culture is now spreading all over the world, thanks to the simplicity of an electronic setup (compared to that of a band, for example), cheaper costs of travel, equipment required and smaller spaces. The skills and techniques required to learn and master DJing and production have also become more easily accessible due to the far reaching effects of global communication and the internet. This connected aspect also helps the modern electronic music producer explore new and old genres and trends from all over the world.

The skills utilized in the production of electronic music or DJing involve those of both solo practice and community interaction (Thomson, 2012), not unlike the context of musicians performing and practicing within an ensemble or band. However in the former case, the presence of an ensemble or a band is not compulsory and thus while both contexts are similar, they are not the same. The large amount of choices and means for experimentation are also widened by the use of technology, but the context and usage of these means of experimentation may or may not be successful within a community based on the social and cultural trends that dominate at the given time. Each art or musical work constructs connections to both prior and future or prospective works (Born, 2005) and it is up to the artist to choose the technology suitable to create the sounds that resonate with these trends. Thus, in a way, the artist acts as a mediator between technology and culture and often these two aspects become so intertwined that one cannot propagate without the other. For example, dance music production has grown from club culture, in which the performing DJ is at the centre of dissemination, and its intended reception by a club audience provides the focus for musical ingredients (Thornton, 1995) while on the other hand, hip-hop style production has developed through turntablism, in which many of the techniques of the turntablist form the basis for arrangement and composition of Hip-hop styles of music in which techniques are used to specifically reference or authenticate the work (Schloss, 2004). While the technology forms one part of the music making process, the methodology employed by the artist in using the technology is what gives his/her work a sense of uniqueness. Rhythm is at the forefront of musical experience in electronic dance music. It constitutes one of the most essential facets of electronic music and is a skilled task requiring time and commitment from the electronic music producer. Regardless of category, each popular electronic musician requires specific skills, techniques, musical knowledge of rhythm and structure as well as an intimate knowledge of creating tonal colors' and timbres through sequencing and arrangement (Fikentscher, 2000). The construction of rhythmic patterns and the production of appealing rhythmic timelines is both a logical and creative process and some of these process can be computationally modeled using algorithms.

Algorithms can be defined as a process or set of rules to be followed to solve a specific problem. When we consider the definition of an algorithm from a standpoint of making and performing music, it becomes clear that several similarities can be drawn. Consider the workflow of a DJ, for example. The said artist would prepare a large range of tracks for a given performance, ensuring that these tracks can be beat matched and fit into a certain tempo range. He/she would then mix these tracks according to the “vibe” or environment in the club/concert, ensuring that the BPM change is adequate and that the mixed tracks go well together. The act of performing and creating music is a process and there are sets of rules to be followed in order for the composition to sound good and/or the performance to stand out. The artist, whether he/she is aware of it or not, acts as an algorithmic designer and it takes a good composer to design algorithms that result in music that captures the imagination (Roads, 1996).

The creative process of making music can be split into small, repeatable tasks that lead to a bigger result. In the case of an instrumentalist this may be the incorporation of a melody or rhythm with the rest of the ensemble, or in splitting up a segment of music into smaller phrases to make the learning and practicing process easier. In the case of an electronic music producer, the end process of a track is often achieved by working on different parts individually, and the styles of approaching this task can vary greatly from one artist to another. The process of composition involves a minutia of manual edition, which could become cumbersome. Algorithmic tools could serve to reduce the boredom and tiresomeness of this process and allow the artist to concentrate on higher-level musical aspects. An algorithmic composition method may be proven successful if it can be incorporated in the workflow of different artists in varied methods and without disturbing his/her natural flow and mental model of the task.

In this thesis, the focus is on providing a method for rhythm alternation in contemporary electronic dance music. My interest in such a method stems from the repeating intention of creating interesting rhythm and variation patterns within my music production workflow and I hope that research done in this direction could help other producers in the same or similar manner. Being a guitarist myself, I have always tended to pay more attention to the melodic and textural aspects of music and though I admire rhythm equally, I don't understand it as well as I understand melody and harmony. By researching rhythm alternation and algorithmic approaches to modifying rhythms, I hope to improve my sense of rhythm and timing while at the same time contribute to research that leads to a method which could be incorporated into the production workflow of artists who wish to experiment with rhythm alternation.

Methods for rhythm alternation and variation are sure to be present in the workflow of any good artist involved in the production of electronic music. Such methods are investigated from multiple perspectives, a few of which can be mathematical (Cao, 2014), musicological (Madden, 2012), cognitive (Carey, Clampitt, 1996), performative (Palmer, 1999) or compositional (Thomson, 2012). Such methods are highly relevant to research that aims to gain a higher level of understanding of the mathematics and geometry of rhythm (Toussaint, 2013), in computer aided compositional tools (Milne, 2016), as well as in the practical workflow of electronic music producers where rhythmic variation is a much sought after effect. By studying the geometry and mathematics of rhythm alternation, it is feasible to provide research that could form the basis for methods, specially those that can be turned

into computer software, which can fulfill some of the requirements of the modern electronic dance music producer.

2 State of the Art

2.1 Social Technologies

Creativity is a social process (Grote, 2014). Musical collaboration forms a part of this process and is usually interactive, consisting of situations with mutual observation and sequences of expressions and reactions. All participants are members of society, feeding their observations made in the creative process back into the social system, from their respective positions. The motivation to create and be an artist is an attempt to encode oneself in the work and their hide away from the looming endless void of death by creating an ambassador that remains (Jenkinson, 2004). This creates a paradoxical situation in which artists create in order to hide, yet at the same time aspire discovery in society to achieve that very goal.

Artists effectively act as social addresses for the music they create. Creativity in this case is more of a case of social collaboration. This collaboration may not be apparent to the public, but nevertheless, it exists (Sawyer, 2007). Artists have to justify their critical steps socially, against a cultural backdrop of having to fit in with the aesthetics dictated by certain genres and styles. In many areas of electronic music, the audiences are composed of listeners with a profound knowledge of the technologies used in the creative process. Even when artists choose to create on their own, they are never really alone with their instruments, at least not when creating anything for a public release.

The beginning of the production process usually starts off with creating a melody, chord progression or rhythmic pattern. Where does this pattern come from? None of these are invented from scratch, but rather the chances are high that you repeat something you have heard many times before, in your personal canon of popular music that has influenced you over the years. Much of popular music comes from this paradigm of starting out by imitation, but then changing the material and adding variations that turn the music into something else, something that can stand as a new, original piece of its own.

2.2 Formatory Universals

There are certain regular forms that are a part of music and which form the building blocks for music making and listening. These formatory universals are discussed in this section.

2.2.1 Meter

When beats are organized into recurring accent patterns, the result is a recognizable meter. The most common meters are diagrammed in figure 2.15.

Figure 2.1: Common meters in music.

Almost all beats can be organized into one of the underlying metrical structures. Further, it is important to note that an underlying meter changes the perception of a rhythmic pattern. For example, the clave son timeline would sound different when played against a quadruple meter and when played against a triple meter.

2.2.2 Rhythm

Rhythms with cycles of 16 pulses comprise binary rhythms and are popular all over the world. In addition to 16, there is another number of pulses that also figures prominently in music of many parts of the world, most notably in sub-Saharan Africa and southern Spain, and this is the number 12. Such rhythms are here called ternary rhythms. Rhythms with 3, 6, and 24 pulses also belong to the family of ternary rhythms. The smallest binary and ternary rhythms with two and three pulses (also called duple and triple rhythms), and their combinations, form the building blocks of most rhythms of the world (Toussaint, 2013).

Figure 2.2: The binary *clave son* (above) and ternary *fume fume* (below) rhythms.

2.3 Overview of Algorithmic Composition

2.3.1 What is an Algorithm

Several general definitions of the term “algorithm” exist in literature, and all of them point towards the idea that an algorithm is a procedure of tasks that lead to a final result. Webster’s dictionary defines an algorithm as “a predetermined set of instructions for solving a specific problem in a limited number of steps.”¹ The Oxford English Dictionary (SECOND EDITION 1989) defines an algorithm as “a process, or set of rules, usually one expressed in algebraic notation, now used in computing, machine translation and linguistics.” (Copley, 2005) Thus we can think of an algorithm as an organized methodology to approach a certain task. The idea of using algorithms or formal processes in the creation of music can be found in various cultures and histories of the world. The 14th and 15th centuries saw the development of the quasi-algorithmic isorhythmic technique, where rhythmic cycles (*talea*) are repeated, often with melodic cycles (*color*) of the same or differing lengths, potentially, though not generally in practice, leading to very long forms before the beginning of a rhythmic and melodic repeat coincide. Compositions based on number ratios are also found throughout Western musical history; for example, Guillaume Dufay’s (1400–1474) isorhythmic motet *Nuper Rosarum Flores*, written for the consecration of Florence Cathedral, March 25, 1436. The temporal structure of the motet is based on the ratios 6:4:2:3, these being the proportions of the nave, the crossing, the apse, and the height of the arch of the cathedral. Mozart is thought to have used algorithmic techniques explicitly at least once. His *Musikalisches Würfelspiel* (“Musical Dice”) uses musical fragments that are to be combined randomly according to dice throws. The *Geniac Electric Brain*² allowed customers to build a computer with which they could generate automatic tunes. Lejaren Hiller (1924–1994) is widely recognized as the first composer to have applied computer programs to algorithmic composition. Hiller used the *Illiac* computer at the University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign, to create experimental new music with algorithms. His collaboration with Leonard Isaacson resulted in 1956 in the first known computer-aided composition, *The Illiac Suite* for String Quartet, programmed in binary, and using, among other techniques, Markov Chains in “random walk” pitch-generation algorithms. Iannis Xenakis was a pioneer of algorithmic composition and computer music. Using language typical of the sci-fi age, he wrote, “With

¹ <https://ccrma.stanford.edu/~blackrse/algorithm.html>

² <http://www.earlycomputers.com/cgi-bin/item-report-main.cgi?20110224>

the aid of electronic computers, the composer becomes a sort of pilot: he presses buttons, introduces coordinates, and supervises the controls of a cosmic vessel sailing in the space of sound, across sonic constellations and galaxies that he could formerly glimpse only in a distant dream" (Xenakis, 1992).

Algorithmic composition, sometimes also referred to as automated composition, basically refers to "the process of using some formal process to make music with minimal human intervention" (Alpern, 1995). Such "formal processes," as we have seen previously; have been familiar to music since ancient times. It follows that algorithmic compositional systems can naturally be used in the workflow of the musician, either by aiding the musician in the compositional or performance process, or by recreating the entire process independently. In this thesis, we focus on the former approach.

2.3.2 Compositional Processes

From a broad perspective, Algorithmic composition can be split into three main categories: stochastic, rule based and artificial intelligence systems². Stochastic systems leave the compositional process to random choice. Such systems can be as simple as generating a random series of notes, as seen in the case of Mozart's *Dice Music* and in the works of John Cage, though a great amount of conceptual complexity can also be introduced to the computations through the computer with statistical theory and Markov chains. Many of the creative decisions in the stochastic method are merely left to chance, essentially the same as drawing notes out of a hat. Another example of non-computer-oriented "stochastic" composition can be found in Karlheinz Stockhausen's *Klaveirstucke XI* in that the sequence of various fragments of music are to be performed by a pianist in random sequence. A different slant to usages of unexpectedness is that of applying chaos theory to algorithmic composition (Burns, 1997). These applications employ various nonlinear dynamics equations that have been deduced from nature and other chaotic structures such as fractals to relay different musical information.

Artificial Intelligence systems are similar to rule based systems, in that they also define a grammar or a set of rules; however, AI systems have the further capacity of defining their own set of rules, giving them a capacity to learn. An example of this is David Cope's system called Experiments in Musical Intelligence (EMI). Like the previous example of Shottstaedt and of Ebcioglu's CHORAL, EMI is based on a large database of style descriptions, or rules, of different compositional strategies. However, EMI also has the capacity to create its own grammar and database of rules, which the computer itself deduces based on several scores from a specific composer's work that are input to it. EMI has been used to automatically compose music that evokes already somewhat successfully the styles of Bach, Mozart, Bartók, Brahms, Joplin, and many others. Another branch of AI techniques is genetic programming. Rather than basing its grammar on scores input to the computer as in EMI, genetic programming generates its own musical materials as well as forms its own grammar. However, the composer must decide which of the material to retain, and which can be discarded as such systems may not give musically relevant output at all stages. Genetic programming comes under the branch of artificial life models, which can be defined as computational models that display some form of emergent behavior that resembles a

biological phenomena of some kind (Miranda, 2002). Other examples of such models are cellular automata and adaptive games. Many Composers have tried out mathematical models, such as combinatorial systems (Dodge, Jerse, 1985), stochastic models (Xenakis, 1992) and fractals (Worral, 1996). These were thought to embody musical composition processes. Some of these trials produced interesting music and much has been learned about using mathematical formalisms and computer models in compositional processes.

Apart from running virtual composers, it is important to take into consideration the meeting point between software and composition. Languages such as Common Lisp Music, Music V and Supercollider have made the process of creating algorithmic music easier, by helping the composer create systems with a certain level of abstraction, so that they don't have to start the process from scratch. More recently, Computer music prototyping environments such as Max/MSP are very popular among artists and musicians looking for customization, experimentation and uniqueness in their workflow. Today Max, Jmax, and Pd can be seen as three very different implementations of the same fundamental idea, each with its own extensions that aren't available on the others. Max is fundamentally a system for scheduling real-time tasks and managing intercommunication between them (Puckette, 2002). Such environments make it simpler to run experiments with unorthodox methods to create algorithmic music, based on the ideas of the electronic music producer.

2.3.3 Creative Freedom in Algorithmic Composition

While studying algorithmic composition in music, it is important to take into consideration the actual usefulness of these algorithmic compositional techniques in the practical workflow of artists working in the production and performance of electronic music. An algorithm that does everything for the composer is neither desired nor necessary. Moreover, the algorithm must fit into the workflow of the music producer without difficulty and must help contribute to the creativity of the musician. This can be achieved either by providing solutions to constraints in the creative process or by providing new avenues for experimentation. David Cope, who is Dickerson Emeriti Professor at the University of California at Santa Cruz, discusses both of these approaches³. For Cope, one of the core benefits of algorithmic composition is that it allows composers to experiment far more efficiently. He is of the opinion that composers who lived prior to the advent of the personal computer had certain practicalities that limited them, namely that it might take months of work to turn an idea into a composition. If a piece is not in the composer's usual style, the risk that this composition may be terrible increases, because it will not be built on the techniques that they've used before and know will generally work. Quoting Cope, "With algorithms we can experiment in those ways to produce that piece in 15 minutes and we can know immediately whether it's going to work or not."⁴ Cope also clearly regards a great many aspects of composition to be algorithmic in nature. He sees constraints as intrinsically linked with algorithmic processes, declaring that, 'Constraints of almost any kind require algorithmic solutions'. Cope's premise is that an algorithm could be defined as nothing more than "a set of rules for solving a problem in a finite number of steps" (Cope, 2000). Cope is not suggesting that a constraint is an algorithm, merely that a stated explicit constraint calls for an algorithmic solution. The constraint is not the algorithm, but a requirement for one (Copley, 2005).

³ <http://artsites.ucsc.edu/faculty/cope/biography.htm>

⁴ <http://www.gizmag.com/creative-artificial-intelligence-computer-algorithmic-music/35764/>

In present times, the use of computers in musical composition has increased significantly. The roles they play in this process can be usefully mapped onto Miranda's distinction (Miranda, 2001), which contains three levels of abstraction:

The microscopic level Here, the composer works with physical sound attributes such as frequency and amplitude, such as granular synthesis.

The note level This level is where sound attributes are bundled together to form a note, such as different harmonics in stringed instruments combining to form a note.

The building-block level This level is concerned with larger musical units lasting several seconds, such as rhythmic patterns, melodic themes and sampled sound sequences.

The work that has been done at the building block level falls primarily under the heading of algorithmic music. It is largely concerned with the application of rules, heuristics, and mathematical formulae to musical composition. In the words of Ada Augusta⁵ '[the Analytical Engine] might act upon other things besides number... Supposing for instance, that the fundamental relations of pitched sounds in the science of harmony and of musical composition were susceptible of such expression and adaptations, the engine might compose elaborate and scientific pieces of music of any degree of complexity or extent.' She further commented, 'The Analytical Engine has no pretensions to originate anything. It can do [only] whatever we know how to order it to perform'. This brings us to the question of creativity in algorithmic composition and it is clear that while algorithmic composition could enhance creativity, it cannot originate it on its own.

According to Copley (2005), Creativity in algorithmic composition is in how the algorithms change through application rather than in the rules or elements of the algorithms themselves. If an individual composer develops an idiosyncratic algorithm for music generation, then the creative endeavor consists of the changes to existing practices necessary for the formulation of the algorithm. We might, if the algorithm was successful, enjoy the output, but another composer is unlikely to feel creatively fulfilled by simply running someone else's algorithm. This is because the composer himself acts as an algorithmic designer since the music making and performing process is intrinsically algorithmic in nature. Thus, a good algorithm is not just one that fits into the workflow of the individual composer who created it, but one that has features that make it desirable in the general workflow of other composers as well. In order to achieve such a feature by modeling musical creative processes, it is crucial that we base our model on something close to what composers actually did, rather than on theoretical constructs, often established long after the creative event and which oversimplify or distort complex thought processes in the interests of pedagogical expediency (Copley, 2005).

Creating music can be a very personal experience for most musicians and the idea that a pre-defined algorithm can create a complete musical unit such as a melody or chord progression without any input required could almost seem like 'cheating'. The idea that

⁵ Published as notes on Menabrea's Notions sur la machine analytique de Charles Babbage (1842), in Richard Taylor's Scientific Memoirs Volume 3 1843.

algorithm use in music removes creativity from composition has been debated over the years (Muscutt, Cope, 2007) along with the concept that using technical and complex tools which require logical or mathematical thought is distinct and counter to the required mindset for composing music (Foxwell, Knox, 2012). While these arguments ring true when viewed from certain directions, they fail to capture the bigger picture that creativity and algorithms can go hand in hand. While music has a strong element of emotion and situation, as a composer or performer at some point you would definitely need logical and mathematical thought. The goal is to find the tipping point, where creativity and logic can go hand in hand without letting one contrasting aspect overpower the other.

Transferring the numerical and logical aspects within an algorithm to a musical function is known as mapping (Foxwell, Knox, 2012). This is where the link between the algorithm and different musical functions such as pitch, timbre, tempo or many other possibilities (Diaz-Jerez, 2000) is forged. A single rule could therefore be attached to these musical parameters (Anders, 2003). Ultimately the mapping is a choice of the creator of the algorithm. Any musical function can potentially be mapped to, therefore the important question is whether the mapped data helps control the sound in a way that it creates a listenable, musical experience which composers can then use. The composer seeking inspiration requires a tool that helps them produce coherent and creatively inspiring music, whilst remaining in control of the creative process. A key point is that the system must help composers augment their existing musical efforts, the algorithm working together with the composer (Foxwell, Knox, 2012).

Apart from these aspects of mapping algorithms to music, it is important to take into account that music is primarily a cultural phenomenon. The need to device generative models within algorithmic composition, which take into account the dynamics of social formation and cultural evolution, have been identified (Miranda, 2002). Also, the issue as to whether computers can create new kinds of music is much harder to study, because in such cases the computer should neither be embedded with particular models at the outset nor learn from carefully selected examples. Stand-alone compositional systems also have a human element to them - the data being crunched to make the composition possible is chosen by humans, if not created by them⁶.

2.3.4 Mapping Structure in Musical Form to Algorithms

Music can be understood as a sequence of sonic events, which move from one time to another. In order to understand music, we take cues or 'earmarks' for further structural guidance beyond the repetition of the structure itself (Cope, 2000). Humans listen for repetition in order to understand the music, this providing the listener with a reference point so the music is coherent (Miranda, 2001). Composers form patterns of rhythm, harmony, melody and interval (Foxwell, Knox, 2012). From the algorithmic point of view researchers have likened the structure of a song to small subunits coming together to help the user build a more complex overall idea (Miranda, 2001). Analysis of music using Hidden Markov Model algorithms has further supported the idea that music can be broken into sub structures (Aucouturier, Sandler, 2001). Structures form an integral part of music and algorithms that

⁶ <http://www.gizmag.com/creative-artificial-intelligence-computer-algorithmic-music/35764/>

map structural elements to musical process and manipulate them can provide interesting creative compositional aids to the music composer. The ability of algorithms in music to create patterns is well known, though enabling them to incorporate things like entropy or recognize the nuances within these patterns and match them off to another pattern is not achieved so easily. The complexity of the algorithm must therefore be considered from the viewpoint of whether it can deal with these factors.

An algorithm can manipulate musical structure and form and creating relationships within melodies and rhythms is key to the music sounding natural to the listener (Foxwell, Knox, 2012). Algorithmic compositional systems that deal specifically with musical structure are what interest us, as we deal heavily with musical structure. One such system, dealing with musical structure in melody generation uses a two stage genetic algorithm, with an 'intervals evaluation function' and a 'ratios evaluation function' comprising the main parts of the algorithm (Khafia, Foster, 2006). In the first stage, the intervals evaluation function distinguishes between acceptable and unacceptable jumps between notes. Accepted transitions include a "Step" which is a difference of 1 or 2 half steps, a "Skip" which is a difference of 3 or 4 half steps and a "Leap" which is a difference of 5, 6, or 7 half steps. A difference of more than 7 half steps is deemed unacceptable. The ratios' evaluation function stems from the basic idea that a good melody contains a specific ideal ratio of notes, and any deviation from that ideal ratio results in a penalty.

2.4 Algorithmic Composition of Rhythm

Here we introduce a study of rhythm from the perspective of algorithmic composition. Section 2.2.1 delves into previous and existing approaches to mapping rhythm. Section 2.2.2 explores the importance of 'intervals' or spaces between the onsets in a given rhythm. Section 2.2.3 employs a study of the properties of rhythmic timelines, such as evenness and off beatness to help gain an understanding of what properties make a rhythm more appealing to a listener. Section 2.2.4 addresses the idea of combining different rhythmic timelines together to form a hierarchy.

2.4.1 Approaches to Mapping Rhythm

Rhythms can be seen as two-way infinite binary sequences [11], where each bit represents one unit of time called a pulse; a 1-bit represents a played note or onset and a 0-bit represents a silence (for example, a sixteenth rest) (Gomez-Martin et al, 2008). As we have seen in the previous section, transferring the numerical and logical aspects within an algorithm to a musical function is known as mapping (Foxwell, Knox, 2012). In this section, we explore several methods employed by other researchers to mapping rhythm in algorithmic composition. The BeatTable (Bumbacher et al, 2013) seeks to create a learning environment that builds upon learners' previous conceptions in the domain of rhythm and proportion in order for them to learn those concepts, which are challenging topics for learners (Abrahamson, 2004; Bamberger, 2003). The BeatTable uses physical interaction to build representational mapping of the concepts of ratio and proportion in rhythmic composition.

Mapping in the BeatTable is done by drawing on the concepts of complex systems and agent-based modeling⁷. Rhythm is generated in a decentralized manner, in such a way that the sound patterns and rhythms perceived by the user emerge as a global phenomenon from local interactions of “virtual agents” with their virtual environment. These virtual agents are referred to as “pulses”, which can be considered to be the basic units that drive sound generation. A pulse can travel through the 2D space of the music environment, which in this case is the 2D plane of the table surface. The pulses act upon their environment, by interacting with the virtual representations of the tangible objects that the user can manipulate. Thus, the audible sound patterns merge directly from the local dynamical behavior of the active pulses and the spatial configuration of the objects.

Another example of an algorithmic rhythm generator is the BeatBender, which is a computer music project that explores a method for generating emergent rhythmic drum patterns using the subsumption architecture (Levisohn, Pasquier, 2008). Rather than explicitly coding symbolic intelligence into the system using procedural algorithms, BeatBender uses a behavior-based model that facilitates emergent expression. The system uses the subsumption architecture developed by Rodney Brooks (Brooks, 1991). Subsumption architecture systems are designed to respond to stimuli in the environment using a hierarchical set of rules. Depending on the state of the environment, different rules of varying complexity are invoked, generating the behavioral output of the system. From an artistic perspective, the rules used to define the agent behavior provide a simple but original composition language, which allows the composer to express simple and meaningful constraints that direct the behavior of the agent-percussionists. From these mappings, the rhythmic output is formed.

An approach that uses natural language text as the basis for rhythm generation also opens up interesting ideas for research (Rangarajan, 2015). Here, the rhythm is mapped to the letters of the alphabet based on the frequency of occurrence of the letter in English⁸. The most frequent letter is "e" and it gets a duration of 1 whole note. Letter 'a' is second in the order and so it gets 1/2. The letter "i" is 4th and it gets 1/4 and so on. Thus, a letter gets assigned a duration inversely proportional to its position in the frequency scale.

Virtual Studio Technology (VST) is a software interface that integrates software audio synthesizer and effect plugins with audio editors and recording systems. Euclidean beats are rhythmic timelines that are generated using the euclidean algorithm (see Appendix A, Euclidean Beats). A VST approach to generating euclidean beats is described in Imogen Heap’s Box of Tricks⁹. The Euclidean Beats module is advertised as “An exciting way to generate complex beats, based on Euclidean mathematics”. The module uses the euclidean algorithm to evenly space a number of steps or hits across the bar. The demo video doesn’t disappoint, which in addition to euclidean beat generation, provides other interesting modifications in terms of timbre, effects and layers to make a creatively appealing tool for rhythm generation.

⁷ <http://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/>

⁸ <http://www.oxforddictionaries.com/words/which-letters-are-used-most>

⁹ <http://www.soniccouture.com/en/products/28-rare-and-experimental/g50-box-of-tricks/>

2.4.2 Beat Intervals in Rhythm

In this section, we explore the importance of beat intervals in rhythm. Several popular rhythms in world history have distinct and distinguishable inter-onset intervals (Toussaint, 2013). Toussaint further explores the characteristics of these inter-onset classes, to determine what actually makes a good rhythm. Beat intervals are important because they define exactly how the silences fit in between the beat onsets, and this is partly responsible in instilling a sense of groove and meter in the listener. An example of an algorithm, which defines a rhythm as a sequence of sonic events arranged in time and thus primarily characterized by their inter-onset intervals, can be found in the work of A. J. Milne (Milne, 2015). It follows that inter-onset intervals are a relevant musical function to be mapped to in an algorithmic sense.

When these interval sets are mapped visually using geometric means, it is possible to draw several distinctions and comparisons between different rhythmic timelines. For example, the *fume-fume* and *son* rhythms are found to both start and end at the same pulses respective to their meters ([3-3-3-3] and [4-4-4-4]). Both the rhythms contain regular meter, and thus can be easily interchanged during the performance of a piece. Such timelines, which contain unequal values of pulses in their cycles, but similar inter-onset interval structures, have been penned as “transformational analogues” by Jeff Pressing (see Appendix A, Binary & Ternary Rhythms). Drawing such observations by comparing two rhythms would not be possible without a study of beat intervals.

Figure 2.3: The *Fume fume* (above) and *Son* (below) timelines. Black rectangles represent onsets. Notice that they both start and end at the same relative pulse positions with respect to the underlying meter. Also, they are similar with respect to their inter onset interval structure and display identical rhythmic contours.

Beat Intervals are also used to derive the concept of rhythmic contours. The rhythmic contour of a rhythm is obtained by coding the change in the durations of two adjacent inter-onset intervals using 0, +1, and -1 to stand for equal, greater, and smaller, respectively. These are relevant from the perceptual point of view because humans have an easier time perceiving qualitative relations such as “less than” or “greater than” or “equal to” than quantitative relations such as the second interval is four-thirds the duration of the first interval (see Appendix A, Binary & Ternary Rhythms).

Toussaint (Toussaint, 2013) defines two or more rhythms to be of the same “Necklace” if they are rotations of each other and to be “Bracelets” if they have the same interval content but are not rotations of each other. This concept of necklaces and bracelets provides a

convenient means to categorize and compare rhythms based on their inter-onset intervals (see Appendix A, Necklaces & Bracelets). The property of off beatness is also measured based on inter-onset intervals (see Appendix A, Off-Beat Rhythms). Complementary Rhythms are also described based on inter-onset intervals, as well as Phantom Rhythms (see Appendix A, Complementary Rhythms & Phantom Rhythms). All of these concepts are further explored in the next section.

Figure 2.4: Two rhythms that are rotations of each other and thus constitute the same necklace.

Figure 2.5: Two rhythms that contain the same interval content constitute bracelets.

2.4.3 Properties of Rhythm Timelines

In this section, we are going to define several rhythm properties such as Evenness and Off Beatness. **Evenness** (Clough and Douthett 1991; Amiot 2007) is a notable property of rhythms, which is much sought after since it creates uniform timelines with an appealing metrical structure for listeners. The evenness of a rhythmic stream is the extent to which its events' sizes are equal (or, equivalently, the extent to which that rhythm is isochronous). When a rhythmic stream is perfectly even, it has translational symmetry at the most granular level possible. It also has reflectional symmetry and is perfectly balanced (Milne et al, 2015). The most common meters in western music, such as 4/4, 3/4 and 6/8, exemplify perfect evenness at all levels.

Figure 2.6: A perfectly even 8-pulse rhythm.

Alternatively, evenness can be defined as the similarity of a rhythm with M events to an isochronous rhythm also with M events (Milne, 2015). This definition implies that a maximally even rhythm of M beats has isochronic beats, or in other words is perfectly even. When certain common constraints are applied to the metrical structure, isochronous beats that also coincide with isochronous pulses become impossible to achieve. For example, consider a twelve-pulse, five-beat rhythm: the two numbers are coprime so, as just indicated, there is no way for the beats to fall on pulses and also be isochronous (perfectly even) under the constraint that all beats must coincide with a pulse. It is possible to maximize the evenness of the beats under these same constraints, however: We have to choose the most even arrangement of five beats (i.e., the beats are not isochronous), whose total length equals twelve isochronous pulses. Such a rhythmic timeline, which cannot achieve perfect evenness, but rather can be arranged in such a way that it is as “even” as possible, display the property of maximal evenness. Preserving this property forms the basis for generation and modification of rhythmic timelines. In the approach followed by Milne, an additional constraint called well-formedness is added. Well-formed patterns are a superset of the previously described $\gcd(M,N) = 1$ patterns, and they are a method for generalizing the latter

into contexts with a non-isochronous pulse or no underlying pulse. The constraint is that basically the inter onset interval sizes are limited to two recurring values, one “short” value and one “long” value. a ratio (long/short) is defined which is one of the principal parameters used to control the rhythmic output (Milne, 2015).

Figure 2.7: The maximally even version of the *fume fume* timeline. Notice that this pattern is also a well formed one.

Four operations that preserve the maximal evenness property, namely *shadow*, *complementation*, *concatenation*, and *alternation* can be defined (Gomez-Martin et al, 2008). The *shadow* of a rhythm is formed by considering the mid-points in interval space between two consecutive onsets. These midpoints themselves may be interpreted as determining another (silent) rhythm lurking in the subconscious mind like a phantom of the rhythm actually sounded (see Appendix A, Phantom Rhythms). A *complement* of a rhythm is formed by exchanging the onsets between the silent and sounded pulses (i.e. if one rhythm contains onsets in the silent pulses of the other rhythm, they form a complementary set) (see Appendix A, Complementary Rhythms). *Concatenation* is the process of joining two rhythmic timelines to form a longer, but maximally even resulting timeline. The *alternation* operation transforms every other onset of a rhythm R into a silence. Every rhythm has two alternations: an even alternation, where we keep the first onset, and change the second into a silence; and an odd alternation, where we keep the second onset, and change the first into a silence. All of these operations can provide interesting rhythmic variation, while preserving maximal evenness to form usable and aurally appealing patterns.

Off Beatness is another property, which acts as a mathematical measure of syncopation. If a piece of music uses a particular regular meter that has strong beats at say pulses zero, three, six, and nine then notes that are played on the other eight pulses are considered to be off-beat relative to such a meter. The off beatness measure is easily generalized to other even values of the number of pulses. For 16-pulse cycles, the offbeat onset positions are {1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15} and for 24-pulse cycles, the offbeat onset positions are {1, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23}. High off beatness creates more syncopated rhythms (see Appendix A, Off-Beat Rhythms).

Figure 2.8: Off beat positions for a 16 pulse cycle (unshaded rectangles)

2.4.4 Hierarchy of Rhythm

When different rhythmic timelines are combined together, they form a hierarchy of rhythm. Mixing rhythms in different interval classes together can make several interesting combinations. Further, by assigning different timbres and drum hits to each rhythmic timeline in the layers hierarchy, interesting effects of grouping and meter can be instilled in the listener (Toussaint, 2013). Combining non-isochronous rhythms with isochronous rhythms is also an appealing choice and such metrical structures can be found in jazz, progressive rock, sub-Saharan African music (Rahn 1986), and Eastern European aksak (Fracile 2003).

By using the constraint of well-formedness described in the previous section, we can combine different well formed rhythms within a hierarchy. This is a convenient method to follow, since it has been proven that a given well-formed rhythm is always nested inside a larger well-formed rhythm (Milne, 2015). By nested, we mean that every event in one pattern (the subset) coincides with an event in the other (the superset). Such fully well-formed hierarchies are useful for providing a rule based solution to create rhythms with a unique sense of groove and meter. The well-formed constraint can be added to any rhythm, by limiting its inter-onset sizes to only the largest and the smallest, and approximating the rest of the intervals to these two values.

2.5 Rhythm Universals

In this section, we discuss universals in rhythm. There seems to be a preference towards certain types of rhythmic patterning, as such patterns are recurrent both in the musical history of the world and popular contemporary culture. Here we study the properties of such rhythms to see why they stand out, and to quantify said properties to help construct universally appealing rhythmic timelines. Section 2.3.1 outlines a study of the properties of the most popular timelines in order to understand why they recur so frequently in popular music and in the cultural history of the world. Section 2.3.2 discusses the social factors that influence universally appealing rhythms. Section 2.3.3 talks about universal forms in music, specifically binary and ternary forms in meter and rhythm.

2.5.1 Properties of Universal Timelines

According to Toussaint (2013), out of the 4368 possible rhythms with 5 onsets and 16 pulses, 6 have made a significant mark as timelines in the music of the world. These are:

- *Shiko*
- *Son*
- *Rumba*
- *Soukous*
- *Gahu*
- *Bossa-nova*

In this section, we measure the properties of these 6 timelines and comparing them to the *Son* rhythm timeline in particular since this timeline has overshadowed the others by capturing the human imagination (Toussaint, 2013).

2.5.1.1 Maximal Evenness

As we have seen in section 2.2.3, in order to maximize the evenness of a given timeline, we have to choose the most even arrangement of the five non-isochronous beats. The *Son* timeline consists of 5 onsets, which are distributed among 12 pulses. Since the number of onsets and the number of pulses are co-prime (this means that their greatest common divisor is unity), there is no way for the beats to be isochronous and also to coincide with pulses.

A distance measure, such as the directed swap distance between a given rhythm and the perfectly even rhythm may serve as a measure of evenness of the given rhythm. The directed swap distance can be defined as the minimum total number of swaps needed by all the attacks of the denser rhythm to convert it to the sparser rhythm, with the constraints that every attack of the denser rhythm must move to an attack position of the sparser rhythm, and every attack of the sparser rhythm must receive at least one attack of the denser rhythm (Toussaint, 2013). The swap distances between the four-beat rhythm and the six distinguished timelines are given by *shiko* = 4, *son* = 5, *rumba* = 4, *soukous* = 6, *bossa-nova* = 6, and *gahu* = 7. According to this measure of maximal evenness, the *son* has a relatively low score of five, and is thus a fairly regular rhythm. A mid-score for this property seems to favor the overall appeal of the timeline.

Figure 2.9: Directed swap distance between the *clave son* timeline and a perfectly even four-pulse rhythm. As we can see, the cost of all the shifts adds up to give the value of 5. The directed swap distance for the other timelines can be calculated in exactly the same manner.

2.5.1.2 Off Beatness

In the 16-pulse cycle in which the six distinguished timelines live, there are four main beats occurring at pulses 0, 4, 8, and 12, which divide the cycle into four equal parts. Relative to these main beats, the remaining onsets may be considered to be off the beat. As explained previously in section 2.2.3, off beatness is a mathematical definition of a property related to the concept of syncopation, and a rhythm that has this property is usually considered to be more interesting and lively. The *clave son* in Figure 2.8 has an off beatness value of one since it has only one onset at one of these positions (pulse two).

Figure 2.10: The *Clave Son* timeline.

Figure 2.11: Off beat positions for a 16 pulse cycle (unshaded rectangles).

2.5.1.3 Rhythmic Oddity

A rhythm with an even number of pulses in its cycle is said to exhibit the rhythmic oddity property if no two of its onsets divide the rhythmic cycle into two half-cycles or segments of equal duration. Figure 2.10 illustrates the presence or absence of the rhythmic oddity property in the six distinguished timelines. It can be seen that *gahu*, *soukous*, and *shiko* do not have the property.

Figure 2.12: Rhythmic oddity in the six distinguished timelines.

The set of antipodal pulses of a rhythm can be defined as the pulses diametrically opposite to the rhythm's onsets. Figure 2.10 shows the six distinguished timelines with lines connecting their onsets to their antipodal pulses. In order to measure the amount of rhythmic oddity in a rhythm, we can use a version of the swap distance in which, for each onset of the rhythm, the minimum distance to its nearest antipodal pulse is calculated. The sum of these

distances over all the onsets of the rhythm provides a measure of rhythmic oddity for the given rhythm.

Consider the calculation of the amount of rhythmic oddity contained in the *gahu* rhythm. The distance from the first onset to its nearest antipodal pulse is two, realized by either pulse 2 or pulse 14. The distance of the second onset to its nearest antipodal pulse (pulse two) is one. The distance of the third onset to its nearest antipodal pulse is zero, since it is itself an antipodal pulse of the fifth onset. The fourth onset is at distance one from pulse 11. Finally, the fifth onset has distance zero since it lies at the antipodal pulse of the third onset. Therefore, the overall oddity score of *gahu* is four. The oddity values of the remaining five timelines increase from left to right with the following values: five for *rumba*, five for *soukous*, six for *shiko*, six for *bossa-nova*, and seven for *son*. We note that the *clave son* has the highest value of rhythmic oddity and this is one of the few properties for which the *clave son* takes on an extreme value when compared to the other five timelines.

2.5.1.4 Metrical Complexity

For a timeline with 16 pulses, the hierarchy of accents or metrical weights is as shown in figure 2.11 (Lerdahl & Jackendoff, 1985). This metrical hierarchy may be used to design a precise mathematical definition of syncopation known as metrical complexity.

Figure 2.13: The metrical hierarchy of Lerdahl and Jackendoff.

Consider the *clave son* timeline shown in figure 2.12 in box notation directly below the metrical hierarchy. The *clave son* consists of onsets at pulses 0, 3, 6, 10, and 12, with metrical weights equal to five, one, two, two, and three, respectively. These metrical weights express how normal or typical it is for a beat to occur at that pulse location according to the theory of Western music practice expressed by Lerdahl and Jackendoff.

Figure 2.14: The metrical complexity of the clave son.

To measure the total metrical expectedness (or simplicity) of the rhythm, we may add the metrical weights of all its onsets. Thus, for the *clave son*, the metrical expectedness is equal to 13. To convert this measure to a measure of metrical complexity or syncopation, it suffices to subtract the metrical expectedness value of a given rhythm with k onsets and n pulses from the maximum possible value that any rhythm with k onsets and n pulses may have. For a rhythm with five onsets and 16 pulses, the maximum expectedness value is 17, obtained by summing the column heights at pulses 0, 8, 4, 12, and any one of 2, 6, 10, and 14. The six distinguished timelines in increasing the value of metrical complexity are: *shiko* = 2, *son* = 4, *rumba* = 5, *gahu* = 5, *soukous* = 6, and *bossa-nova* = 6. Once more, the range of values is between two and six, and *son* has a value that falls in the middle of this range.

2.5.1.5 Main Beat Onsets

The six distinguished timelines have four main beats at pulses 0, 4, 8, and 12, as indicated in Figure 2.13 by means of double circles. The number of onsets of a 16-pulse rhythm that coincide with these four beats is a measure of the rhythm's synchronicity with the underlying beat. The number of main beats contained in each of the six distinguished timelines is: *shiko* = 3, *son* = 2, *rumba* = 2, *soukous* = 1, *bossa-nova* = 1, and *gahu* = 1. The range of values is from one to three, and the *son* moreover falls squarely in the middle.

Figure 2.15: Four main beats of 16 pulse timelines.

2.5.1.6 Distinct Durations

A numerical method to represent the interval content of a rhythm is by listing how many times each possible distance occurs. In the case of 16-pulse rhythms, the possible distances range from one to eight, and the interval content can be represented as the numerical set (0, 1, 2, 2, 0, 3, 2, 0). This is known as the interval vector of the rhythm. A more visually compelling representation of the interval vector is as a histogram. Figure 2.14 shows the histograms of the six distinguished timelines.

Figure 2.16: Interval content histograms of the six distinguished timelines.

This entropy is an implicit measure of the number of distinct durations present in the rhythm. A higher value of entropy results from a flatter histogram, which in turn implies the presence of a wider range of distinct durations. The number of distinct durations may also be measured explicitly by just counting them. From the histograms in Figure 2.14, the following data may be readily observed: *shiko* = 4, *bossa-nova* = 4, *son* = 5, *rumba* = 6, *soukous* = 7, and *gahu* = 7. The values range from four to seven, and the *clave son* falls in the lower-middle range.

2.6 Summary

Section 2.4.2 explains the importance of beat intervals in rhythm. These intervals give us a convenient means to label rhythms and compare them. Additionally, in section 2.5.1.1 and 2.5.1.2, we define two variables, directed swap distance and off beatness. These variables are calculated from the interval contents of a given rhythm. Using the concept of beat intervals to alternate rhythms, we need to quantify how useful these generated rhythms can be in the production process of an electronic musician. In order to achieve this, we define three variables, *similarity*, *continuation* and *interestingness*. These variables are defined as follows:

- *Similarity* measures if the rhythmic timelines with alternated intervals are perceptually similar to each other
- *Continuation* measures if the rhythmic timelines with alternated intervals are suitable to be used as a transition or extension from one timeline to the next.
- *Interestingness* identifies which of the rhythmic timelines with alternated interval contents are interesting.

We proceed in the methodology to measure the effect of the directed swap distance and off beatness on these three variables, i.e. *similarity*, *continuation* and *interestingness*.

To summarize, in section 2.1, we took a look at the importance of social impression and collaboration in the creation of music. Particularly, we note that this influences the creative process of the musician. In section 2.2, we look at the basic building blocks of meter and rhythm. In section 2.3, we provided an overview of algorithmic composition. Section 2.4 outlines the approaches to mapping rhythm in various existing compositional systems and the importance of beat intervals in rhythm composition. Section 2.5 discusses universals in rhythm and why they are important. Following a study of these concepts, we now present a method for rhythm alternation that takes into accounts all of these principles, while retaining a unique contribution value.

3 Methodology

In this chapter we describe the methodology applied in our research. This can be split into three main steps:

- Analyze a seed rhythm and extract beat intervals. We specifically use a seed rhythm to give the composer the creative freedom to use a rhythm of his or her choice, as well as to use rhythms that have been proven to be appealing. (See section 2.5)
- Use multiset permutations to generate all possible non-repeating variations of the extracted beat intervals. This constitutes the algorithmic composition part of the method.
- Generate a set of rhythms according to the previously obtained variations of beat intervals that make up the **interval combinatorial class** of the given seed rhythm.
- Evaluate the set of rhythms in terms of *similarity*, *continuation* and *interestingness* to determine if these rhythms can provide a suitable method for rhythm alternation, to be used in the music production process to enhance the creativity of the music producer. The terms *similarity*, *continuation* and *interestingness* in the present context are defined here:
 - *Similarity* measures if the rhythmic timelines within the generated interval combinatorial class are perceptually similar to the original (seed) timeline.
 - *Continuation* measures if the rhythmic timelines within the generated interval combinatorial class are suitable to be used as a transition or extension to the original (seed) timeline.
 - *Interestingness* identifies which of the rhythmic timelines of the interval combinatorial class are interesting.

Each step is further elaborated in the following sections.

3.1 Identification of Seed Rhythms

In order to generate the interval combinatorial class, we need a reference rhythm, or a seed rhythm, that acts as the basis for the interval set permutations. For our research, several popular world rhythms and rhythms with aurally appealing properties as outlined by Toussaint form the basis or seed rhythms. The following seed patterns were used. Each seed is followed by a graphical representation for comparison:

- Tresillo

- George Gershwin's "I Got Rhythm"

- Anacrusis

- Flat Rhythms

- Fume Fume

- African 7 Onset Rhythms

- Cinquillo

- Clave Son

- Bossa Nova

- Soukous

3.2 Interval Set Extraction

Each of the identified rhythms consists of a unique interval set. This set is extracted and identified. For example, the interval set for the *clave son* is [3-3-4-2-4] and the interval set for the *fume fume* is [2-2-3-2-3], as shown in figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Graphical representation of the interval sets for the *clave son* (above) and *fume fume* (below) rhythms.

3.3 Generation of Interval Combinatorial Class

From each of the interval sets extracted as above, we can generate the interval combinatorial class in two steps as outlined below:

- Treat each interval set as a multiset. A multiset is a set that allows repetition in its elements. This is required because interval sets contain repetitions of the same elements. For example, the interval set of the clave son [3-3-4-2-4] partly consists of repetitions of the elements '3' and '4'.
- Generate a multiset permutation for each multiset. This is carried forward in the R programming environment using the 'multicool' package (Williams, 2009) using the following commands for the interval set of the clave son:
 - **library(multicool)**
 - **x = c(3,3,4,2,4)**
 - **m = initMC(x)**
 - **allPerm(m)**

These generated interval set permutations, when treated as a set of beat intervals, constitute the interval combinatorial class of the given seed rhythm.

3.4 Mapping Beat Intervals to Timbre Sets

Each generated interval combinatorial class consists of a set of similar rhythms, and can now be mapped to different timbres, for example, the different parts of the drum kit. For our research, each Interval Combinatorial Class is mapped to different elements of the 808-drum machine. The choice of timbres is arbitrary, and is based on creative preference; for example, sparser rhythms are more suited to be mapped to a kick drum, while denser rhythms are more suitable to be mapped to higher frequency timbres such as hats or maracas. The mapping followed by us is as listed:

- Claps
 - Tresillo
 - George Gershwin's "I Got Rhythm"
 - Anacrusis
 - Flat Rhythms
- Hats and Maracas
 - Anacrusis
 - Fume Fume
 - African 7 Onset Rhythms
 - Cinquillo
- Kicks
 - Clave Son
 - Bossa Nova
- Clave
 - Soukous

3.5 Combinatorics and Hierarchies

Once each interval class is generated and mapped to different timbre sets, we can experiment with combining them to create unique metrical and perceptual effects. For example, by mixing rhythms within the same interval combinatorial class mapped to different timbre sets, such as mixing two different rhythms within the *cinquillo* combinatorial class but assigning one to hats and the other to maracas, creates the rhythmic canon effect (Toussaint, 2013). Also by mixing a binary rhythm such as the *clave son* with a ternary rhythm such as the *fume fume*, we can create polyrhythmic hierarchies. By experimenting in this manner, these rhythms and their generated interval combinatorial classes can be used to create a possibly infinite set of rhythms suitable to be used in the production workflow of an electronic music producer.

3.6 Evaluation

The evaluation was conducted with an online survey the link to which can be found in Appendix B, thanks to Carthach Onuanain¹⁰ who provided the scripts for the survey. Two different seed rhythms were used for each part. For the similarity and continuation cases, the Cuban *cinquillo* rhythm and the 9 other rhythms that form its interval combinatorial class were used. Finally, for the interestingness case the *fume fume* rhythm and its 9 interval counterparts were used. The seed rhythms and their interval contents are as shown in figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: The *cinquillo* rhythm with interval content [4-2-4-2-4] (above) and the *fume fume* rhythm with interval content [2-2-3-2-3] (below).

The method followed for the evaluation is listed for each dependent variable as follows:

3.6.1 Similarity

The *cinquillo* rhythm and the rhythms that form its interval combinatorial class were used for this case study. The interval content of the seed remains the same at the beginning of each comparison as [4-2-4-2-4]. The values for the responses to the question “Are the two patterns contained in each clip similar to each other?” range from 1-5 with the following legend:

¹⁰ <http://carthach.tk>

- 1 - Dissimilar**
- 2 - Somewhat Dissimilar**
- 3 - Similar**
- 4 - Very Similar**
- 5 - Extremely Similar**

3.6.2 Continuation

Here again, the *cinquillo* rhythm and the rhythms that forms its interval combinatorial class was used. The seed rhythm [4-2-4-2-4] is alternated with its interval counterparts for each case. The values for the responses to the question “Do the two patterns contained in each audio clip continue smoothly into each other?” range from 1-5 with the following legend:

- 1 - Highly Disagree**
- 2 - Disagree**
- 3 - Neutral**
- 4 - Agree**
- 5 - Highly Agree**

3.6.3 Interestingness

The *fume fume* rhythm and the rhythms that form its interval combinatorial class were used for this case study. Each pattern is played for 1 bar and the responses to the question “Do you find the patterns contained in each audio clip to be interesting?” are recorded. The response values range from 1-5 with the following legend:

- 1 - Not Interesting at All**
- 2 - Not Interesting**
- 3 - Neutral**
- 4 - Interesting**
- 5 - Very Interesting**

In the next chapter, the results of the evaluation survey, measures for comparison and summary statistics are provided.

4 Results

Each of the seed rhythms mentioned in section 3.1 are assigned to a timbre set as outlined in section 3.4 with the help of Ableton Live¹¹ using the provided software emulation of the 808 drum machine. The live set with all of the world rhythms mapped to timbre sets is provided as a free download, the link to which can be found in Appendix B. From this set, The *cinquillo* and *fume fume* interval classes were isolated and the patterns that form their respective interval combinatorial classes were exported against a 4/4 reference rhythm to be used in the online evaluation survey, the link to which can also be found in Appendix B.

The online evaluation was carried forward with the help of 20 participants comprised of friends and colleagues with a basic to expert knowledge of electronic music and rhythm. The participants were asked the questions “How often do you casually listen to music?”, “How often do you focus listen to music?”, “Do you play an instrument?”, “Do you play a percussive instrument like a drum?”, and “Do you read music?”. The Casual Listening and Focus Listening responses are recorded with a rating from 1 – 5 with the following legend:

- 1 – Never**
- 2 – Almost never**
- 3 – Sometimes**
- 4 – Often**
- 5 – Very Often**

The rest of the questions are recorded in the form of “yes” and “no” responses. The demographics and responses are displayed in table 4.1.

Gender %	Median Age	Casual Listener (Mean)	Focus Listener (Mean)	Instrument %	Percussion %	Read %
61% Male	25-34	4.5	3.8	61% Yes	17% Yes	33% Yes
39% Female				39% No	83% No	67% No

Table 4.1: Participant demographics

In order to compare the results, we can use measures such as the directed swap distance as described in section 2.5.1.1 and off beatness as described in section 2.5.1.2. The directed swap distance provides a measure of maximal evenness, while the off beatness provides a measure of syncopation. The maximal evenness property provides a convenient means to compare results for the similarity and continuation cases, while the off beatness value should favor interestingness (Toussaint, 2013). In this chapter, the values of these measures is calculated and listed for each case of similarity, continuation and interestingness.

¹¹ <https://www.ableton.com/en/live/>

The directed swap distance for the *cinquillo* and its interval counterparts are calculated as illustrated in figure 4.1 and figure 4.2.

Figure 4.1: Directed swap distance calculation for the *cinquillo* seed timeline. The distance measure can be determined by adding the swaps at the bottom. In this case the value is 4.

Figure 4.2: Directed swap distance calculation for pattern 2, set 2 in the *cinquillo* interval combinatorial class. In this case the value is 2.

As explained in section 2.5.1.2, the off beatness of a given rhythmic pattern can be measured by counting the number of off beat positions of the onsets in the said pattern. The off beatness of the *fume fume* seed timeline can be calculated as 2, since two of the onsets are in off beat positions as shown in figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3: Off beat positions for the *fume fume* timeline.

4.1 Similarity

The directed swap distances for the patterns in each similarity set is as shown in table 4.2. SD 1 and SD 2 correspond to the swap distances for pattern 1 and pattern 2 respectively. Mod (SD1 – SD2) is the mod difference between the two swap distances.

Set	Pattern 1	SD 1	Pattern 2	SD 2	Mod (SD1 – SD2)
1	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	[2-4-2-4-4]	4	0
2	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	[2-2-4-4-4]	2	2
3	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	[4-2-2-4-4]	2	2
4	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	[4-4-2-2-4]	2	2
5	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	[4-4-4-2-2]	2	2
6	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	[2-4-4-4-2]	8	4
7	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	[4-2-4-4-2]	6	2
8	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	[4-4-2-4-2]	4	0
9	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	[2-4-4-2-4]	6	2

Table 4.2: Swap distances for similarity sets.

The mean, variance and standard deviation for each similarity set is as shown in table 4.3.

Set	Mean	Variance	Standard Deviation
1	3.1	1.04	1.02
2	2.15	0.76	0.87
3	3.05	0.57	0.75
4	3.05	1.10	1.05
5	2.4	0.88	0.94
6	2.2	1.32	1.15
7	3.4	0.98	0.99
8	3.2	1.22	1.10
9	3.2	0.48	0.69

Table 4.3: Summary statistics for similarity sets.

We proceed to relate the mod difference **Mod (SD1 – SD2)** and the **Mean** from tables 4.2 and 4.3 respectively by calculating the correlation coefficient between these two sets of values. The individual values are tabulated in table 4.4.

Set	Mean	Mod (SD1 – SD2)
1	3.1	0
2	2.15	2
3	3.05	2
4	3.05	2
5	2.4	2
6	2.2	4
7	3.4	2
8	3.2	0
9	3.2	2

Table 4.4: Mean and mod difference values for similarity sets.

The correlation coefficient between these two sets of values is calculated to be **-0.54**. This shows a negative correlation between the *similarity* and the positive difference of swap distance between each set of similarity patterns. In other words, similarity sets with a closer swap distance values favor *similarity* by 0.54 correlation in the current sample set.

4.2 Continuation

The directed swap distances for the patterns in each continuation set is as shown in table 4.5. SD 1 and SD 2 correspond to the swap distances for pattern 1 and pattern 2 respectively. Mod (SD1 – SD2) is the mod difference between the two swap distances.

Set	Pattern 1	SD 1	Pattern 2	SD 2	Mod (SD1 – SD2)
1	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	[2-4-2-4-4]	4	0
2	[2-2-4-4-4]	2	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	2
3	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	[4-2-2-4-4]	2	2
4	[4-4-2-2-4]	2	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	2
5	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	[4-4-4-2-2]	2	2
6	[2-4-4-4-2]	8	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	4
7	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	[4-2-4-4-2]	6	2
8	[4-4-2-4-2]	4	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	0
9	[4-2-4-2-4]	4	[2-4-4-2-4]	6	2

Table 4.5: Swap distances for continuation sets.

The mean, variance and standard deviation for each continuation set is as shown in table 4.6.

Set	Mean	Variance	Standard Deviation
1	4.06	0.56	0.75
2	3.41	1.01	1.00
3	3.41	1.13	1.06
4	3.58	1.26	1.12
5	2.70	1.09	1.05
6	3.47	1.26	1.12
7	3.94	1.05	1.03
8	3.76	0.44	0.66
9	3.64	0.61	0.78

Table 4.6: Summary statistics for continuation sets.

We proceed to relate the mod difference **Mod (SD1 – SD2)** and the **Mean** from tables 4.5 and 4.6 respectively by calculating the correlation coefficient between these two sets of values. The individual values are tabulated in table 4.7.

Set	Mean	Mod (SD1 – SD2)
1	4.06	0
2	3.41	2
3	3.41	2
4	3.58	2
5	2.70	2
6	3.47	4
7	3.94	2
8	3.76	0
9	3.64	2

Table 4.7: Mean and mod difference values for continuation sets.

The correlation coefficient between these two sets of values is calculated to be **-0.42**. This shows a negative correlation between the *continuation* and the positive difference of swap distance between each set of continuation patterns. In other words, continuation sets with a closer swap distance values favor *continuation* by 0.42 correlation in the current sample set.

4.3 Interestingness

The *fume fume* timeline is a 5 onset, 12-pulse rhythm and hence it does not have a perfectly even version. We calculate the swap distance between each pattern in the interval combinatorial class and the maximally even version of the *fume fume* rhythm. The off beatness and swap distance values of each pattern in the *fume fume* interval combinatorial class is as shown in table 4.8.

Pattern	Off Beatness	Swap Distance
[2-2-3-2-3] (Seed)	2	4
[2-2-2-3-3]	1	5
[3-2-2-2-3]	4	2
[3-3-2-2-2]	1	1
[2-3-3-2-2]	1	1
[3-2-3-2-2]	2	0
[2-3-2-3-2]	2	2
[2-2-3-3-2]	1	3
[3-2-2-3-2]	3	1

Table 4.8: Off beatness and swap distance values for the *fume fume* interval combinatorial class.

The mean, variance and standard deviation for each pattern in the interestingness case is as shown in table 4.9.

Pattern	Mean	Variance	Standard Deviation
[2-2-3-2-3]	3.35	1.12	1.05
[2-2-2-3-3]	3.41	0.88	0.93
[3-2-2-2-3]	3.17	1.40	1.18
[3-3-2-2-2]	3.64	0.86	0.93
[2-3-3-2-2]	3.23	1.19	1.09
[3-2-3-2-2]	3.53	1.51	1.23
[2-3-2-2-2]	3.76	0.94	0.97
[2-2-3-3-2]	3.06	0.93	0.96
[3-2-2-3-2]	3.35	0.99	0.99

Table 4.9: Summary statistics for interestingness ratings.

We proceed to relate the **Off Beatness** and **Swap Distance** values from table 4.8 to the **Mean** in table 4.9 by calculating the correlation coefficient between the **Mean** and **Off Beatness** and the **Mean** and **Swap Distance**. The individual values are tabulated in table 4.10.

Pattern	Mean	Off Beatness	Swap Distance
[2-2-3-2-3]	3.35	2	4
[2-2-2-3-3]	3.41	1	5
[3-2-2-2-3]	3.17	4	2
[3-3-2-2-2]	3.64	1	1
[2-3-3-2-2]	3.23	1	1
[3-2-3-2-2]	3.53	2	0
[2-3-2-2-2]	3.76	2	2
[2-2-3-3-2]	3.06	1	3
[3-2-2-3-2]	3.35	3	1

Table 4.10: Mean, off beatness and swap distance values for interestingness patterns.

The correlation coefficient for the off beatness measure is calculated to be **-0.13** and the correlation coefficient for the swap distance measure is calculated to be **-0.23**. Both these values are relatively low compared to the similarity and continuation cases. Thus, for the interestingness case, we cannot conclude a correlation and further trials with a bigger and more specific demography are required to see if a higher correlation can be established.

5 Conclusions

The aim of the research conducted in this thesis was to investigate a method for rhythm modification that is simple, effective and fits into the workflow of the electronic music producer. Such a method was found with the utilization of beat intervals and a study of the properties of rhythms.

By generating a multiset permutation of a given set of beat intervals, it was found that several rhythms could be extracted from a single seed rhythm. Further, these rhythms can be organized in terms of *similarity* and *continuation* by comparing the swap distance of the input seed rhythm and the generated rhythms within the interval combinatorial class of the seed rhythm. As shown in the chapter 4, rhythms with a smaller difference in swap distance are more similar and form a better continuation to each other while rhythms with a bigger difference in swap distance. In section 2.5.1.2, we showed that the off beatness is a mathematical definition of a property related to syncopation. Thus, the off beatness measure can be used to classify the rhythms within the interval combinatorial class in terms of syncopation value.

Beat intervals form the basis for the research carried forward in this thesis. They were shown to provide a convenient means to compare and alternate rhythms and the alternated rhythms were observed to be similar and form a good continuation to the original seed rhythm. Thus, it is feasible to use any given rhythmic pattern and provide a palette of alternated rhythms that can be used to enhance the creativity of the electronic music producer.

Since the sample demographic is currently limited to only 20 participants, the correlation found cannot be said to be completely conclusive. However, it provides a strong pointer that there is a correlation between *similarity*, *continuation* and the positive difference of the swap distance of the compared rhythms. Further studies with a larger and more organized demographic could provide more insight. By using more specific sets of demographics, such as targeting the survey to a set of musicians and music producers and comparing these results to those obtained with a demographic which consist of mostly casual listeners, we could compare and test the correlation between these variables to see if people who work with music tend to favor the ratings more than casual listeners. The *interestingness* case failed to provide any conclusive results, which is indicative that the either the variable must be redefined to be more specific or that the study must be conducted with a larger or more specific demographic.

Although the off beatness value is better suited to be a measure of syncopation, it remains to be seen if the difference in off beatness between rhythms in the *similarity* and *continuation* sets could influence the ratings for these variables.

Several important world rhythms were studied and their interval sets were used to create interval combinatorial classes. Researching such rhythms helped us find patterns that are appealing to listeners and this study helped me personally improve my rhythm composition skills in the production of electronic music. Creating and using multiset permutations of beat

intervals is a simple and effective way to create novel rhythmic variations and enhance the creative process of the electronic music producer.

5.1 Future Work

A rhythm alternation generator remains to be implemented. Such a generator would take as input a seed rhythm pattern, and provide all the patterns that constitute its interval combinatorial class. The rhythms can be classified in terms of *similarity*, *continuation* and *off beatness*. In addition, the following controls are to be implemented:

- **Evenness / Maximal Evenness:**
 - Binary Timelines: Gradient control to shift onsets to even metrical positions (so the rhythm moves towards perfect isochronicity).
 - Ternary Timelines & Timelines where perfect evenness is not possible : Gradient control to achieve maximal evenness in the given timeline (the most even distribution possible given the pulse and onset constraints).
- **Complement:** Complement a given rhythm timeline by exchanging the onsets between the silent and sounded pulses.
- **Alternation:** Transform every other onset of a rhythm into a silence.
 - Even Alternation: keep the first onset and change the second to a silence, repeat till end of timeline.
 - Odd Alternation: keep the second onset and change the first to a silence, repeat till end of timeline.
- **Off Beatness:** If a piece of music uses a particular regular meter that has strong beats at say pulses zero, three, six, and nine then notes that are played on the other eight pulses are considered to be off-beat relative to such a meter. By using a gradient control to shift the onsets to off beat positions more (or less) syncopation can be introduced into the timeline.

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Appendix A: Summary of The Geometry of Musical Rhythm: What Makes a "Good" Rhythm Good? By Toussaint, G. T. (2013)

1 What is Rhythm?

- Rhythm is often regarded as one of the most problematic and least understood aspects of music.
- The difficulties of dealing with rhythm are immense.
- The temporal flow of music is primarily a matter of rhythm.
- Rhythm is: everything.
- Rhythm is the language of time.
- Rhythm is created whenever the time continuum is split up into pieces by some sound or movement.
- Even before we come into this world, while we are still in the womb, we are already bathed in the steady comforting rhythm of our mother's thumping heartbeat and her smooth breathing.
- Rhythmic grouping is a mental fact, not a physical one.
- Many of the most important rhythmic structures are present only in the physical signal or the symbolic score.
- Rhythm is the manifestation of a process that emerges from the amalgamation of a physical signal with perceptual and cognitive structures of the mind.

2 A Steady Beat

- A succession of sounds of equal duration, with invariable intensity and identical timbre, do not constitute a rhythmic event. A more appropriate term for such a sequence is arguably a pulsation.
- A sequence of spoken digits with evenly spaced acoustic onsets was judged to be uneven by listeners.
- Rhythms perceived by the human mind are not veridical representations of the written score or its realization by the human voice or a musical instrument. Rhythm perception emerges from the interplay between the bottom-up, data-driven, outer stimuli emanating from the world, and the top-down, conceptually driven, inner response mechanisms of the mind's ear.

3 Timelines, Ostinatos, and Meter

- Timelines are more particular ostinatos that are easily recognized and remembered, play a distinguished role in the music and also serve the functions of conductor and regulator, by signaling to other musicians the fundamental cyclic structure of the piece.

- Meter is usually defined in terms of a hierarchy of accent patterns, and considered to be more regular than rhythm.

4 The Wooden Claves

- Played as a sound that appears to be produced by a material that resonates somewhat like a crystal and a little like metal

5 The Iron Bells

- The dawuro (also called atoke, banana, or boat bell) is shaped somewhat like a canoe or taco shell, as pictured in Figure 5.2. To play it, the bell is balanced delicately in the palm of one hand, and the edges of the bell are struck with a metal rod. The sound is a piercing reverberation that resembles a whistle, and cuts through a score of drums. Furthermore, by muting the sides of the bell with the thumb after striking it, a variety of interesting sustained sound effects may be produced. Two traditional timelines played with this bell, and used in the adowa drum music of the Ashanti people of Ghana are [x . x . x . . x . x x .] and [x . . . x . . x . x . .].

6 The Clave Son

- At an abstract level, all rhythms can be classified into families described by these two numbers: the onset-number and the pulse-number.
- For example, the number of rhythms with five onsets and 16 pulses corresponds to the number of ways of selecting five items from among 16.
- There is a well-known combinatorial formula for this type of calculation that yields the solution. The formula is given by $(16!)/((5!)(11!))$, where the symbol “!” is pronounced factorial, and $k!$ denotes the product of the k terms $(k)(k - 1)(k - 2)(k - 3)$.
- Of course, not every rhythm in this family is considered to be a “good” rhythm, in the sense that it has been adopted as a timeline pattern in traditional music somewhere on the planet.
- In contrast, one of the main goals of this book is precisely the design of algorithms for generating good rhythms using simple mathematical principles.
- A natural question that comes to mind, besides the reason for the choices of $n = 16$ and $k = 5$ to begin with, is how, out of the 4368 myriad possible rhythms with five onsets from among 16 pulses, this particular configuration of inter-onset intervals [3-3-4-2-4] managed to become such a catchy and widely used rhythm.

7 Six Distinguished Rhythm Timelines

- out of the 4368 possible rhythms with 5 onsets and 16 pulses, it is difficult to find more than a dozen traditional 5-onset, 16-pulse timelines. Of these, 6 have made a significant mark as timelines in the music of the world.
 - Shiko
 - Son
 - Rumba
 - Soukous
 - Gahu

- Bossa-nova
- Finally, we remark that starting the shiko on the second onset is also a popular pattern found in Arabic rhythms played on a drum. Here again some notes are low sounds whereas others are high pitched. The maqsum is given by [X x . x X . x .], and the baladi by [X X . x X . x .]. The masmudi is a slow baladi, and the sáidi has duration intervals [X X . X X . x .].* The durational pattern in these last three Arabic rhythms is the same, and it is only the pitch (or timbre) of the drum notes that varies from one rhythm to another.
- One property that all six distinguished rhythms have in common is that they all use adjacent inter-onset durations with values equal to one, two, three, or four. Interestingly, ancient Chinese philosophers at the time of Confucius regarded these four numbers as “the source of all perfection”.

8 The Distance Geometry of Rhythm

- Music is like geometric figures and numbers, which are the universal forms of all possible objects of experience.
- The geometric approach used here permits a new kind of analysis of rhythms that yields novel insights, and thus augments the traditional tools employed by musicologists.
- It is extremely difficult to perceive temporal symmetry.
- When the mind is presented with a rhythm such as the clave son that is repeated continuously throughout a piece of music, and that has a cycle that lasts only a few seconds, it is natural to ask whether it perceives durations other than those that occur between adjacent onsets. There exists plenty of evidence, and consensus, that the “conscious present” (also called “specious present”) lasts for about 3 s. This phenomenon is known as the “three-second window of temporal integration”.
- Therefore, it is most likely that the mind also perceives (perhaps unconsciously) the durations between all the other pairs of onsets, in rhythms that last less than 3s.
- In the present context, one measure of the complexity of a rhythm is the total number of different distances that it generates. Therefore, one would expect the gahu to be more complex than the shiko, and perhaps more challenging to learn as well.

9 Classification of Rhythms

- Starting from the acoustic signal produced by an instrument, there are several stages in any musical rhythm recognition system.
- A fundamental and difficult first step is the analysis of the acoustic waveform, to detect and estimate the locations of the onsets. Once these onsets are established, a matching is sought between the query rhythm to be classified, and the stored templates.
- This matching problem is made easier if the underlying fundamental beat is also known.
- The Methodology involves a decision tree that classifies the rhythms based on geometric properties.

10 Binary & Ternary Rhythms

- Binary Rhythms contain cycles with 2, 4, 8, 16, 32 pulses.
- Ternary Rhythms contain cycles with 3, 6, 12, 24 pulses.
- The smallest binary and ternary rhythms with two and three pulses (also called duple and triple rhythms) and their combinations form the building blocks of most rhythms of the world, leading some scholars to label them as music universals.
- There are other musicological structural similarities between the two rhythms. For example, both numbers 12 and 16 may be evenly divided into four equal durations (quarter measures) without requiring additional pulses, by selecting the “north” “south” “east” and “west” pulses numbered 0, 3, 6, and 9 in the ternary case and 0, 4, 8, and 12 in the binary case. These are the four most salient locations for regular metric beats in families of rhythms with 12 and 16 pulses.
- **The fume-fume and son rhythms both have their first and last onsets on their “north” and “west” metric pulses, respectively. Since both regular meters, [3-3-3-3] and [4-4-4-4], can be easily aligned with each other, and the two rhythms are so similar, they can easily be interchanged during the performance of a piece.**
- Jeff Pressing calls such timelines with unequal values of pulses in their cycles, but with similar inter-onset interval structures, transformational analogues, and Fernando Benadon explores their use as compositional and analytical expressive transformations of each other.
- In addition to the fact that the two rhythms are quite similar to each other with respect to the exact locations of their attacks, they are in fact identical to each other if they are represented by their rhythmic contours.
- The rhythmic contour of a rhythm is obtained by coding the change in the durations of two adjacent inter-onset intervals using 0, +1, and -1 to stand for equal, greater, and smaller, respectively. The durational patterns of the fume-fume and son timelines are, respectively, [2-2-3-2-3] and [3-3-4-2-4]. Therefore, both rhythms have the same rhythmic contour: [0, +1, -1, +1, -1].
- Rhythmic contours are relevant from the perceptual point of view because humans have an easier time perceiving qualitative relations such as “less than” or “greater than” or “equal to” than quantitative relations such as the second interval is four-thirds the duration of the first interval.
- Two rhythms with the same contour may also sound quite different, as is the case for the 16-pulse and 11-pulse rhythms with inter-onset intervals [4-3-2-3-4] and [3-2-1-2-3], respectively.
- Therefore, used in isolation or in a context where the intervals can vary widely, the rhythmic contour suffers from severe drawbacks as a representation from which to extract meaningful rhythmic similarity features.

11 The Isomorphism of Rhythm and Scale

- From the musical point of view, 12 has the important property that it is a small number that contains many divisors other than one and 12, in particular two, three, four, and six.
- Twelve is also the number of different pitches in the chromatic scale or octave of the modern piano keyboard that consists of 12 pitch intervals called semitones.

- The bembé rhythm and the diatonic scale are isomorphic to each other, they are the same pattern of long and short intervals, one expressed in time intervals and the other in pitch intervals.

12 Binarization, Ternarization and Quantisation of Rhythms

- The Cuban ethnomusicologist Rolando Pérez Fernández hypothesized that the African ternary rhythms were binarized by means of cultural blending caused by human migrations, and that the ternary fume-fume rhythm was, thus, converted to the binary clave son rhythm.
- To convert binary rhythms to ternary rhythms from a geometric standpoint, the following rules may be followed :
 - If the onset of the ternary rhythm coincides with a pulse of the binary rhythm, then the onset stays where it is.
 - If the onset of the ternary rhythm falls anywhere in between two binary pulses then it snaps to the binary pulse that follows it (rounding up).
- In attempting to explain the perceptual mechanism by which ternary rhythms could be converted to their binary counterparts, two different geometric models have been uncovered for converting the ternary fume-fume to the binary clave son.
- Which of these geometric models best fits the perceptual mechanism at work will, in the end, have to be determined by psychological experiments.

13 Syncopated Rhythms

- Syncopation is the spice of rhythm.
- The regular shifting of each beat in a measured pattern by the same amount ahead of or behind its normal position in that pattern.
- Syncopation is a momentary contradiction of the prevailing meter.
- Syncopation from a mathematical point of view is vague because we are trying to define with precise mathematical tools a slippery human perceptual skill.
- Although syncopation in music is relatively easy to perceive, it is more than a little difficult to define precisely.
- In 1996, Fred Lerdahl and Ray Jackendoff published a book titled *A Generative Theory of Tonal Music*, in which they proposed a hierarchy of accents for musical rhythm inspired by research work in linguistics.
- For a timeline of 16 pulses, their hierarchy of accents or metrical weights may be expressed by constructing a graph.
- First, starting at pulse zero, and proceeding from left to right, assign a weight of one to every pulse (shown as shaded boxes). Second, in a similar manner, increment by one the weight of every second pulse. Third, increment by one every fourth pulse. Next, increment by one every eighth pulse, and finally every 16th pulse. The resulting height of the column at any pulse gives the weight or degree of accent given to an onset that occurs at that pulse.
- **This metrical hierarchy may be used to design a precise mathematical definition of syncopation, which we shall call metrical complexity.**
- To measure the total metrical expectedness (or simplicity) of the rhythm, we may add the metrical weights of all its onsets. Thus, for the clave son, the metrical expectedness is equal to 13.

- To convert this measure to a measure of metrical complexity or syncopation, it suffices to subtract the metrical expectedness value of a given rhythm with k onsets and n pulses from the maximum possible value that any rhythm with k onsets and n pulses may have. For a rhythm with five onsets and 16 pulses, the maximum expectedness value is 17, obtained by summing the column heights at pulses 0, 8, 4, 12, and any one of 2, 6, 10, and 14. This value is realized by several rhythms, including the popular classical music ostinato rhythm [4-4-2-2-4] with onsets at pulses 0, 4, 8, 10, and 12. Thus, the metrical complexity of the clave son is $17 - 13 = 4$. For comparison, the more syncopated clave rumba that has its third onset at pulse number seven has a metrical complexity equal to $17 - 12 = 5$.
- Possibility to experiment with the methodology of constructing the weights profile can be explored.
- Michael Keith proposed a mathematical measure of syncopation in the context of sustained musical notes that is defined by onsets as well as offsets.
- To construct his weighted general measure of syncopation, Keith assigns to hesitation a weight of one. He considers anticipation to be a stronger form of syncopation than hesitation, and therefore gives anticipation a weight of two. Finally, since syncopation combines both hesitation and anticipation, he adds these two weights together to obtain a weight of three for syncopation.

14 Necklaces & Bracelets

- A rhythm and a rotated rhythm are different from the point of music making. However, it is obvious that the interval contents of these two durational patterns and their resulting histograms are identical, since the interval content of a rhythm is invariant to its rotations.
- Therefore, from certain analytical perspectives the two rhythms may be considered to be the same. In the mathematical field of combinatorics, the two rhythms in Figure 14.1 are said to be instances of the same necklace. In the pitch domain in music theory, a necklace corresponds to a chord type.
- It is possible to have two rhythms that are not instances of the same necklace and that still have the same interval content, namely, if one rhythm is the mirror image of the other. To include such cases, we use the mathematical term bracelet.
- Number of unique necklaces = number of onsets.
- One way to measure the robustness of the effectiveness of a necklace as a template for the design of rhythm timelines is by the number of its rotations that are actually used in practice.
- A rhythm necklace that has the property that all its onset rotations are used as timelines in practice will be called a robust rhythm necklace.
- The Tresillo timeline is one instance of a robust rhythm necklace.
- Possibility to experiment with necklaces of all rhythm timelines can be investigated.
- Mixing binary and ternary necklace timelines to generate unique patterns can be investigated
- **Aksak necklace has been incorporated into jazz as well as modern art music in the twentieth century.** Dave Brubeck used this pattern as the meter in one of his best-selling compositions Rondo a la Turk.
- The most frequent of these is Rotation 0, followed in decreasing order by Rotation 3, Rotation 1, and Rotation 2. This preference may be explained in terms of Gestalt

psychology principles. **That Rotations 0 and 3 are preferred over the other two follows perhaps from the fact that rhythms are most easily perceived as starting or ending with the longest gap**, in this case three pulses.

- Furthermore, Rotation 0 has a greater surprise value, or in technical terms, a more pronounced Gestalt despatialization effect, due to the fact that the initial regular pattern [2-2-2] creates the expectation of the complete cycle [2-2-2-2], which is suddenly broken by the introduction of a three-pulse interval to yield the irregular rhythm [2-2-2-3].
- Another well-known robust rhythm necklace is the five-onset, eight-pulse pattern known as the Cuban cinquillo pattern.
- Another important family of necklace is the fume-fume pattern or ternary clave-son (5-onset 8 pulse).
- Perhaps, the most important necklace in sub-Saharan Africa is the seven-onset, 12-pulse group of bell rhythms (highly useful).
- In these examples, the numbers of onsets and pulses are relatively small. This appears to be a requirement for a timeline necklace to be robust. As these values become large, the number of rotations also grows, reducing the fraction of these that remain salient.

15 Rhythmic Oddity

- East London, acid jazz music and the ancient Aka Pygmy music of Central Africa have pieces of music that possess the rhythmic oddity property.
- While studying the music of the Aka Pygmies of Central Africa, Arom noticed that their music contained rhythmic timelines that exhibited a property that he christened rhythmic oddity.
- A rhythm with an even number of pulses in its cycle has this property if no two of its onsets divide the rhythmic cycle into two half-cycles, that is, two segments of equal duration.
- For rhythms to be effective as timelines, they should in general not contain silent gaps longer than half of their cycle, and they should exhibit a certain degree of regularity or near-evenness. These two constraints are often enough to inadvertently prevent the rhythmic oddity property from being satisfied.
- Arom defined the rhythmic oddity property in the form of a strict binary category, that is, a rhythm either has or does not have the rhythmic oddity property.
- This concept may be extended by means of a multivalued function that measures the amount of rhythmic oddity that a rhythm possesses. This function (rhythmic oddity) depends on the number of violations of the rhythmic oddity property present in a rhythm.
- Then, **the fewer equal bipartitions a rhythm admits, the more rhythmic oddity it possesses.**
- The relevance of necklaces here comes from the fact that the rhythmic oddity function is independent of the rotations of a rhythm.
- **necklace + rhythmic oddity to create pattern variations can be investigated**
- Among this family of rhythms there may have been an evolutionary preference for those that admit as few as possible equal bipartitions, and thus a higher degree of rhythmic oddity.

- One application of the rhythmic oddity property is to the algorithmic generation of “good” rhythms.
- Let us assume that we want to generate a rhythm with five onsets in a cycle of 12 pulses.
- The first onset is placed at pulse zero. This implies that the diametrically opposite pulse six is now unavailable for placing an onset, since we want the rhythmic oddity property satisfied. To place the next onset, we hop to pulse two, making pulse eight unavailable.
- This process is continued, always advancing by hopping a distance of two units if this is possible.
- When this is not possible, as is the case when we want to hop to onset number four at pulse six (which is unavailable), we try the next pulse (here pulse seven). If it is available (as it is in this example), we take it. Otherwise, we continue skipping pulses until an available pulse is found. Since in this case we advanced by a distance of more than two pulses, we call this a jump.
- The Hop-and-Jump algorithm is obviously guaranteed to yield rhythms with the rhythmic oddity property since it never places an onset on an unavailable pulse location.
- **Using different numbers of onsets and pulses, and different sizes of hops the Hop-and-Jump algorithm is successful at generating good timelines.**
- This property is used in cosmic girl (jamiroquai).
- Hop and jump with 9 onsets and 32 pulses yields the rhythm and necklacing it gives the jamiroquai pattern.

16 Off-Beat Rhythms

- Many rhythm timelines cannot be discriminated solely on the rhythmic oddity function.
- To resolve this, a new mathematical measure of syncopation known as off beatness is employed.
- Consider a cycle of 12 pulses. Such a cycle may be evenly divided (without remainder) by the integers two, three, four, and six, to yield the four regular rhythms with inter-onset intervals [6-6], [4-4-4], [3-3-3-3], and [2-2-2-2-2-2].
- If a piece of music uses a particular regular meter that has strong beats at say pulses zero, three, six, and nine then notes that are played on the other eight pulses are considered to be off-beat relative to such a meter.
- The positions 1, 5, 7, 11 are considered to be strongly off beat.
- The set of four off-beat pulse positions {1, 5, 7, 11} has an interesting mathematical interpretation as well. These numbers are the numbers between 0 and 12 that generate (visit) all 12 pulses when we travel along the circle starting at zero and advance in steps of size equal to the number.
- The off beatness measure is easily generalized to other even values of the number of pulses. For 16-pulse cycles, the off-beat onset positions are {1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15}.
- For 24-pulse cycles, the off-beat onset positions are {1, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23}.
- The off beatness property provides a tool for categorizing rhythms.
- Off beatness measures a type of mathematical syncopation.
- high offbeatness creates better (syncopated) rhythms.

17 Rhythm Complexity

- Rhythm is arguably the most fundamental aspect of music, and complexity is one of its most salient features.
- A musical concept closely related to rhythm complexity is syncopation.
- Rhythmic complexity and off-beatedness are two examples of rhythmic complexity.
- Concerning the measurement of rhythmic complexity, Martin Clayton writes: "I can think of no objective criteria for judging the relative complexity or sophistication of rhythm in, for example, Indian raga music, Western tonal art music, and that of African drum ensembles.
- The concept of complexity is extremely fluid. Its definition depends to a great extent on the context and the purpose to which it is put.
- In an information theory context, a metronomic pulsation is least complex, and random noise is most complex. However, in a musical context, random noise is not complex at all.
- The most complex musical rhythms exhibit a degree of complexity that lies somewhere between complete order and complete disorder.
- Ilya Schmulevitch and Dirk-Jan Povel distinguish between three broad categories of complexity measures for musical rhythms: hierarchical, dynamic, and generative.
- Hierarchical measures refer to structure at several levels simultaneously, dynamic measures refer to the nonstationarity of the input over time, and generative measures depend on the amount of effort required to generate the rhythms.
- The usefulness of a measure depends on its intended application.
- Predictability implies simplicity, whereas nonpredictability or randomness implies complexity.
- At present, it appears that information-theoretic measures per se are not able to capture well the human perceptual, cognitive, or performance complexities of short musical rhythms such as timelines.

18 Dispersion Problems and Maximally Even Rhythms

- Deals with the analogous dispersion problem of locating k points on a circle so as to maximize the sum of their pairwise distances.
- How should a set of k points on a circle be arranged so that the sum of their pairwise arc-lengths is maximized.
- The structure of this solution is completely different from the case in which the points fall on a straight line, and might raise hopes that the sum of pairwise arc-lengths might be used either as a criterion for generating regular rhythms or perhaps maximally even rhythms, or for measuring how regular they are for the purpose of their automatic classification.
- Rhythms other than maximally even or regular, and even highly irregular rhythms, can also maximize the sum of pairwise arc-lengths. A rhythm is maximally even if its attack points are distributed in time as evenly as possible.
- Perfectly even rhythms are those consisting of k onsets placed so that they correspond to regular k -sided polygons on the continuous circle of time.
- Maximally even rhythms are those that correspond to polygons that are almost regular.

19 Euclidean Rhythms

- The pleasure we obtain from music comes from counting, but counting unconsciously. Music is nothing but unconscious arithmetic.
- The Euclidean Rhythm generation algorithm works by considering the smaller number to be associated with the number of onsets that we want the rhythm to have, and the larger number with the total number of pulses that determine the rhythmic span or cycle.
- The family of rhythms generated with the Euclidean algorithm are known as Euclidean rhythms because they are generated using the structure of the Euclidean algorithm, and will be denoted by $E(k,n)$, where k is the number of onsets and n is the number of pulses in the cycle. Thus, the Cuban tresillo is denoted by $E(3,8)$.
- When the number of onsets is greater than the number of silent pulses, all the silent pulses are moved in the first step of the algorithm.
- Generate new rhythms using $E()$.
- **Rotate each new rhythm to create variations (each is its own necklace).**
- Displace onsets symmetrically to make variations.

20 Leap Years, The Rhythm of the Stars

- A more elegant structural approach to designing rules for the introduction of leap years in calendars is based on the idea of rhythmic cycles.
- The leap year pattern of the Jewish calendar is a Euclidean necklace.
- All the intervals in the diatonic scale are increased by one to obtain the Jewish leap year pattern. In musical terms, they have the same rhythmic contour.
- Another structural design of a calendar that uses cycles is the Islamic calendar, which is based on the time between two successive new moons (lunations), and in which 1 year is defined as 12 lunations.
- The leap year pattern of the Islamic calendar is also a euclidean necklace.
- The Jalali leap year pattern introduced into the Persian calendar is also a Euclidean necklace.

21 Approximately Even Rhythms

- There exist many rhythm timelines in cultures all over the world that have the property that they are Euclidean or maximally even.
- However, for every fixed pair of values of n and k , the Euclidean algorithm yields only one rhythm necklace.
- **Consider for instance the Euclidean rhythm obtained when $n = 8$ and $k = 2$. Since eight is divisible by two, the rhythm obtained is $[x \dots x \dots] = [4-4]$. Repeating this pattern yields only a steady pulsation, not a very interesting rhythm. However, if we displace the second attack by one pulse, say to the left, we obtain the very interesting rhythm $[x \dots x \dots] = [3-5]$.**
- Several rhythms used in practice also consist of three onsets among eight pulses, but they are neither euclidean rhythms or rotations thereof.
- To generate a larger, more inclusive class of “good” rhythms, the concept of maximally even has to be relaxed.

- We can generate three new rhythms this way by moving either the second onset from pulse three to pulse two, the third onset from pulse six to pulse five, or both of these.
- **The family of almost maximally even rhythms is made up of the rhythms obtained by all combinations of snapping intersection points to both, the nearest right and the nearest left pulses.**
- For small values of the number of pulses and onsets, all members of the families of almost maximally even rhythms are used in practice as timelines.
- Although the property of almost maximal evenness appears to be almost necessary for a rhythm to be good, it seems not to be sufficient to characterize the rhythms that have been adopted by cultures in the past.

22 Rhythms and Crystallography

- There exist pairs of molecules that have different atomic structures, but yield exactly the same collection of interatomic distances.
- Since one-dimensional “crystals” are periodic patterns much like the keyboard on a piano, which repeat octave after octave, it is possible to take one period of the crystal and wrap it around a circle.
- In mathematical language, they are called circular lattices.
- If one configuration can be brought into correspondence with another by rotations, reflections, or a combination of these operations, then the two configurations are considered to belong to the same bracelet. If reflections are left out of this definition, then we are left with necklaces.
- This topic falls under the discipline of distance geometry, which is concerned mainly with the reconstruction of configurations of points in space from their interpoint distances.
- Finding features of rhythms that characterize their uniqueness and are good for measuring their similarity in a way that correlates well with human judgments is an extremely difficult problem.

23 Complementary Rhythms

- If one rhythm contains onsets in the silent pulses of another rhythm, these are called complementary rhythms.
- **They sound good if they sit in certain frequencies that go well together.**
- Together, they fill the entire set of pulse locations in the cycle, and are thus also referred to as interlocking rhythms.
- Complementary rhythms that have the same number of onsets enjoy the very special and rather surprising property that their inter-onset interval histograms are always identical to each other. In other words, they are homometric.

24 Radio Astronomy and Flat Rhythms

- Radio astronomers are interested in receiving signals from outer space to discover new planets in other solar systems, perhaps stumble on alien intelligent life, as well as answer a variety of questions related to the structure of matter in the universe.

- The problem of distributing radio telescope elements so that all the distances between pairs of elements are different is structurally identical to the problem of designing Golomb rulers.
- A Golomb ruler on the other hand is a ruler with very few marks.
- In a Golomb ruler, one can only measure the distances between pairs of marks.
- The marks in a Golomb ruler are arranged so that as many different distances as possible can be measured.
- If the Golomb ruler measures all the distances ranging from one to the length of the ruler, it is called perfect.
- By connecting the ends of a Golomb ruler together to form a circle, and considering the marks on the ruler as possible positions for the locations of the onsets of musical notes, the ruler determines a rhythm.
- If we replace the straight-line distances between the marks on a ruler by geodesic distances on the circle that represent time durations, then the Golomb ruler problem becomes that of constructing rhythms in which all the inter-onset durations are distinct.
- The difficulty in creating rhythms with distinct inter-onset intervals arises when there are more than three onsets, although such rhythms do exist.
- There are only two rhythm bracelets that have perfect flat interval histograms.

25 Deep Rhythms

- A deep set is a set of pairs of points in which each distance realised by pairs of points should occur a unique (distinct) number of times.
- In other words, no distance occurs the same number of times as any other distance. In other words, the multiplicity of each distance is unique.
- If we convert the plotting space from a 2d plane to a 3d circle, the arrangement becomes relevant for application in rhythm and scale.
- There is a simple algorithm that will generate deep rhythms that are more interesting than those that have all their onsets in one semicircle.
- This algorithm will generate different families of deep rhythms that depend on a parameter "d".
- The algorithm places the first onset at pulse zero. To place the remaining onsets, the pulses in the cycle are scanned in a clockwise order, and a visited pulse is selected as an onset every time a distance d has been advanced.
- The value of d can be any integer that is relatively prime to the number n of pulses in the cycle, that is, n and d have no common divisors other than one.
- When d is relatively prime to n and d is small enough, a new attack is never inserted in a location diametrically opposite to an already-existing attack, thus preserving the property of rhythmic oddity.
- If the Hop-and-Jump algorithm of Chapter 15 is stopped when seven attacks are obtained, then the rhythm necklace generated is the same as the seven-attack rhythm necklace generated with the procedure described here.

26 Shelling Rhythms

- A rhythm admits a shelling, with respect to some property P if there exists a sequence of insertions or deletions of onsets so that, after each insertion or deletion, the rhythm thus obtained continues to have property P.
- The terms “insertions” (or deletions) refer to replacements of a silent (or sounded) pulse with a sounded (or silent) pulse.
- To ensure that the rhythm remains deep when an onset is deleted, the onset to be deleted must contain a spectrum with exactly one instance of every distance present in the histogram of the rhythm before the onset is deleted.
- In this way, the height of each column of the histogram will be reduced by one unit, thus preserving the deepness property.
- **The process of shelling rhythms is a natural technique that is routinely applied by drummers during their solo improvisations, and it can also be used as a composition tool.**
- The minimalist composer Steve Reich applied this technique, which he called rhythmic construction, for the first time in his 1973 piece titled Drumming, and described it as “the process of gradually substituting beats for rests (or rests for beats).
- From the empirical examination of preferred rhythms used in several cultural traditions, it follows that deepness is a mathematical property that appears to reflect this cultural preference.
- Therefore, the process of shelling rhythms while maintaining this property provides an algorithm that may find application to the automatic generation of “good” rhythms.
- The geometric analysis of the shelling technique that Steve Reich used in the construction and reduction phases of the beginning and ending of his piece Drumming reveals that the main property that is preserved during this process may be characterized by the notion of symmetry.
- With the shelling property, we can traverse from any one deep rhythm to any other deep rhythm by a sequence of insertions or deletions of attacks, while preserving the deepness property of all rhythms traversed along the way.

27 Phantom Rhythms

- Phantom Rhythms are formed by considering the mid-points in interval space between two consecutive onsets.
- These midpoints themselves may be interpreted as determining another (silent) rhythm lurking in the subconscious mind like a phantom of the rhythm actually sounded.
- The muscles of the arm change their function in a significant way at these midpoints in time, and thus it is reasonable to hypothesize that the motor system of the brain must register these distinctive moments, either consciously or subliminally.
- Some musicologists such as Gerhard Kubik believe that these shadow rhythms are physiologically and psychologically relevant to the proper study and understanding of rhythm cognition and performance, going as far as to claim that motion and motor action are essential to the explanation of rhythm.

28 Reflection Rhythms and Rhythmic Canons

- If the mirror-symmetric image of a rhythm about some axis of symmetry is equal to its complementary rhythm, such rhythms are known as interlocking reflection rhythms.
- These rhythms also exhibit the phenomenological property that if the rhythm and its complement are both played simultaneously, and their acoustic properties such as timbre or intensity differ, the listener has the impression that the rhythm is switching roles, sometimes acting as a figure with its complement as a background, or vice versa.
- The idea here is that the right and left hands should produce different sounds either in pitch or timbre so that the listener may perceive both the right-hand and left-hand rhythms simultaneously as two separate streams of pulsations.
- **Rhythmic Canons:** A rhythmic canon is composed of two or more rotations of a rhythm played at the same time, with the constraint that each rotation (also called a voice) uses a tone or timbre that is distinguished from the others, and no two onsets (attacks) of different voices sound in unison.
- **Rhythmic canons provide a popular and effective composition technique that can be traced back to Olivier Messiaen, and has recently received a great deal of attention from the music-theoretical and mathematical points of view.**

29 Toggle Rhythms

- Toggle rhythms are those cyclic rhythms that when played using the alternating-hands method, have their onsets divided into two consecutive sets, such that the onsets of the first set are played consecutively with one hand, and subsequently the onsets of the second set are played consecutively with the other hand.
- The most pleasing and interesting results with this method are obtained when the left and right hands strike drums that are tuned differently, so that they produce sounds of distinct tones or timbres.
- By fixing simple repetitive hand motion patterns that a drummer can learn to play automatically without thinking, and then applying simple repetitive attack patterns on the sequence of drums or other instruments such as bells or cymbals, the drummer can engender the emergence of several complex rhythmic patterns being played simultaneously.

30 Symmetric Rhythms

- Symmetry is one of the most consequential features of the world we inhabit. Alexander Voloshinov refers to symmetry as “the most important principle of harmony both in the universe and in art.”
- A palindromic rhythm (also called non retrogradable because it cannot be used as a different new rhythm by merely reversing it in time) exhibits mirror symmetry about a point in time.

31 Odd Rhythms

- Odd rhythms can be defined as rhythms with an odd pulse duration pattern such as 5, 7, 9, 11.
- These can be further classified into straight ahead meters and additive meters.

- Straight ahead meters are those meters that had no accent on any pulse, or have an accent only on the first pulse of the cycle.
- Additive meters are those that consist of a concatenation of groups with at least one group of two pulses and one group of three.

32 Other Representations of Rhythm

- So far, three notations have been used, the box notation (in several variations), the convex polygon notation, and the inter-onset interval vector notation (durational patterns).
- The first two approaches are geometric and emphasize visualization. The third method is a numerical system that indicates duration with numbers.
- Another noteworthy numerical system is gongche notation, the traditional Chinese system that uses numbers to indicate pitches, and dots and lines for rhythm.
- The musical information and the notation systems that encode this information are interdependent. They have their unique advantages and drawbacks, and different applications may benefit more from notation systems that are tailored to them.
- Any rhythm notation system suggests a variety of new methods for measuring the distance (dissimilarity) between rhythms.

33 Rhythmic Similarity and Dissimilarity

- The similarity between two objects is one of the most important features for distinguishing between them and for pattern recognition in general.
- The Hamming distance is perhaps the most natural way to measure the dissimilarity between two rhythms represented as sequences of symbols.
- The Hamming distance between two sequences is defined as the number of corresponding locations where the two sequences differ.
- Measuring the similarity between two symphonies, songs, melodies, or rhythms is a challenging problem in music analysis and technology, and has many applications ranging from generating playlists to copyright infringement resolution, music information retrieval, phylogenetic analysis and discovering the evolution of rhythmic patterns and motifs in a style of music.
- For rhythms represented as binary sequences in box notation, this means that the operation (swap) interchanges an empty box with a filled box when the two boxes lie next to each other.
- The swap distance between two rhythms is defined as the minimum total number of swaps necessary to transform one rhythm to the other, and is equivalent to the minimum value of the sum of distances (measured in number of pulses) traveled by all the attacks (onsets) during this transformation.
- If the two rhythms have a different number of attacks, then it is impossible to convert the sequence with fewer attacks to the sequence with a higher number of attacks, since there are not enough of them.
- **The swap distance may be modified to give the directed swap distance which is defined as the minimum total number of swaps needed by all the attacks of the denser rhythm to convert it to the sparser rhythm, with the constraints that every attack of the denser rhythm must move to an attack position of the**

arser rhythm, and every attack of the arser rhythm must receive at least one attack of the denser rhythm.

- The edit distance between two sequences of symbols is defined as the minimum number of edits (or mutations) necessary to convert one sequence to the other.
- An insertion inserts a symbol into a sequence, thus making it longer. A deletion deletes a symbol from a sequence, making it shorter. A substitution replaces one symbol by another, thus not changing the length of the sequence.
- These operations allow the comparison of sequences of different lengths.
- There is experimental evidence that the edit distance correlates well with human judgments of rhythm similarity.

34 Regular and Irregular Rhythms

- Regular rhythms may be described on the rhythm circle as regular polygons, that is, polygons with all their sides equal and all their angles equal.
- **The mixing of regular and irregular (asymmetric) rhythms is one of the key features of modern electronic dance music.**
- Irregular is the opposite of regular, which in the context of time in musical rhythm means that onsets occur with the same duration between individual adjacent instances.
- Rhythm irregularity is a measure of the amount of unevenness present in the adjacent inter-onset interval durations.

35 Evolution and Phylogenesis of Musical Rhythm

- There is a great deal of mathematical, musicological, and perceptual similarity between the binary clave son given by [3-3-4-2-4] and its ternary counterpart with interval structure [2-2-3-2-3].
- There exists some possible evidence that the ternary version may have mutated to the binary version by a process that ethnomusicologist Rolando Pérez Fernández calls binarization, in the context of intercultural transplantation.
- Flamenco music provides a convenient data set on which to test phylogenetic analysis tools to determine what can be garnered from analyzing the metric patterns.
- Such an analysis may shed light on the evolution of the clave son and its migrations between Ghana and Baghdad, keeping in mind that the simpler a rhythmic timeline is, the higher is the probability that it was born independently in different places, without necessarily migrating from one place to another.

36 Rhythmic Combinatorics

- If the rhythm is viewed as a durational pattern, or a sequence of inter onset intervals, a family of rhythms is obtained from one good rhythm by swapping the positions of the inter-onset intervals of the good rhythm by generating all the permutations of these intervals.
- The clave son pattern in binary sequence representation is [x . . x . . x . . . x . x . . .], which yields the durational pattern [3-3-4-2-4].
- Note that these numbers are multisets since repetitions of the elements are permitted

- We have five intervals that belong to three different classes: one of class one, two of class two, and two of class three. Therefore, the total number of permutations of the interval set [3-3-2-4-2] is $(5!)/(1!)(2!)(2!) = 30$.
- If one rhythm may be obtained from another by a permutation of its interval vector, the two rhythms will be said to belong to the same interval combinatorial class.
- Combinatorial methods such as those described above, for generating and analyzing permutations and combinations of elements in sets, are a technique that has been used frequently by composers.
- the various permutations of a rhythm can be selected either at random or according to some musicological rules.

37 What Makes the Clave Son Such a Good Rhythm?

- Maximal Evenness
 - For a rhythm to be a good timeline, the five onsets should be distributed almost as evenly as possible within the 16-pulse time span.
 - According to this measure of maximal evenness, the son has a relatively low score of five, and is thus a fairly regular rhythm.
- Rhythmic Oddity
 - A rhythm has the rhythmic oddity property if no two of its onsets are located diametrically opposite to each other on the circle.
 - By itself, the property is not sufficient to highlight the clave son uniquely from among the group of six timelines, since the rumba and the bossa-nova also possess this property.
 - One way to measure the amount of rhythmic oddity in a rhythm is with a version of the swap distance in which, for each onset of the rhythm, the minimum distance to its nearest antipodal pulse is calculated. The sum of these distances over all the onsets of a rhythm is a measure of how little oddity the rhythm possesses; a higher value indicates greater rhythmic oddity because the rhythm is then further away from losing the property.
 - The clave son has the highest value of rhythmic oddity among this family of rhythms. This is one of the few properties for which the clave son takes on a complete extreme value when compared to the other five distinguished timelines.
- Off Beatness
 - In the 16-pulse cycle in which the six distinguished timelines live, there are four main beats occurring at pulses 0, 4, 8, and 12, which divide the cycle into four equal parts.
 - Relative to these main beats, the remaining onsets may be considered to be off the beat.
 - Off beatness is a mathematical definition of a property related to the concept of syncopation and a rhythm that has this property is usually considered to be more interesting or lively.
 - Off beatness measure makes sense only when the rhythm is viewed in the context of an underlying regulative beat structure.
- Weighted Off Beatness

- The weighted off beatness measure counts the total number of onsets that are both off-beats and double-time off-beats, but places different weights on each type of off-beat.
- **Metrical Complexity**
 - If for a given rhythm the weights corresponding to the onset locations are summed, we obtain a measure of the metrical expectedness (or simplicity) of the rhythm.
 - For the clave son, the metrical simplicity is 13.
 - The maximum value that five onsets in a cycle of 16 pulses may take is 17.
 - Subtracting 13 from 17 yields the value four as a measure of the metrical complexity of the clave son.
- **Main Beat Onsets and Closure**
 - The six distinguished timelines have four main beats at pulses 0, 4, 8, and 12.
 - The number of onsets of a 16-pulse rhythm that coincide with these four beats is a measure of the rhythm's synchronicity with the underlying beat.
 - A rhythm that has an onset at the last of these four main beats (12) has the additional property of closure.
- **Distinct Durations**
 - The entropy of the full inter-onset interval histograms is an implicit measure of the number of distinct durations present in the rhythm.
 - A higher value of entropy results from a flatter histogram, which in turn implies the presence of a wider range of distinct durations.
- **Distinct Adjacent Durations**
 - Another measure of rhythm complexity counts the number of distinct adjacent inter-onset intervals present in the rhythm.
 - The values for the main timelines are shiko = 2, bossa-nova = 2, son = 3, rumba = 3, gahu = 3, and soukous = 4. The values range from two to four, with son falling midway between these two extremes.
- **Onset Complexity and Distinct Distances**
 - In addition to counting the number of distinct distances between all its pairs of onsets that a rhythm may possess, one may focus on a single onset and measure its contribution to the total number of distinct distances.
 - According to this measure of complexity, the shiko, son, and bossa-nova are all considered equal, and the rumba has the highest complexity. Thus, this measure does not discriminate between the son and the shiko or bossa-nova.
- **Deep Rhythms, Deepness and Shallowness**
 - A rhythm is deep if its full inter-onset interval histogram has the property that no two columns have the same height (not counting the columns of height zero).
 - According to this binary-valued measure, among the six distinguished timelines, only the shiko and bossa-nova are deep.
 - This binary measure may be converted into a multivalued measure of deepness by calculating the distance between the histogram of a given rhythm and that of a deep rhythm.
 - In terms of deepness (or shallowness), the son follows the middle path.
- **Tallness**
 - The tallness property measures the maximum height of the columns in the inter-onset interval histogram.

- A larger tallness value suggests the tendency that there is a larger concentration of inter-onset intervals, and is somewhat related to the deepness property.
- The following values of tallness are evident: soukous = 2, gahu = 2, son = 3, rumba = 3, shiko = 4, and bossa-nova = 4. Once more, the clave son avoids the extreme values that this property takes.
- **Phylogenic Tree Centrality**
 - The application of phylogenetics trees can be applied to the analysis of families of rhythms to obtain a clustering of the rhythms as well as to infer a possible evolutionary phylogeny
 - Applying similar techniques to the six distinguished timelines yields additional insight into the special status enjoyed by the clave son.
 - **The clave son, with the lowest value of six, is the unique rhythm most similar to all the others. This suggests that it is the central rhythm of this family of rhythms. In other words, the clave son is the rhythm that minimizes the total number of swap mutations needed from which to generate all the other rhythms. Therefore, we may consider this number as a measure of the centrality (or proto-typicality) of a rhythm with respect to both a group of rhythms and a specific distance measure**
- **Mirror Symmetry**
 - Symmetry is often cited as a contributing factor to making music sound good
 - Only shiko, son, and bossa-nova possess mirror symmetry, and only the clave son possesses diagonal mirror symmetry.
 - Symmetry by itself is no guarantee that a rhythm that possesses it will be a successful timeline.
- **Shadow Contour Isomorphism**
 - Of the six distinguished five-onset, 16-pulse timelines, the clave son is the only one that has a cyclic rhythmic contour that is the same as the contour of its shadow rhythm.
 - Whether this property has any psychological or neurological weight in restricted contexts has yet to be determined experimentally. However, as a mathematical property, it is clearly useful for characterizing rhythms in general, and the clave son in particular.
- **Of the 12 properties that have numerical values, nine of them yield values that for the clave son fall in the middle of the range spanned by the six rhythms. This list provides strong evidence that at least for the clave son, and perhaps for other rhythms to be good as well, these properties should not take on extreme values, but rather follow the “golden mean.”**

38 The Origin, Evolution and Migration of the Clave Son

- It is well known that human perception does not result from a mere bottom-up processing of the objective scientific stimulus presented to the perceiving mechanism. It is rather a partly subjective and constructive interactive process that also involves top-down processing, in which the perceiver projects a medley of competing hypotheses about what is perceived.
- As long as the instructions are passed along intact, the rhythm produced with them will likely remain the same, barring other drastic outcomes such as a lack of

performance skill. In contrast to the concrete continuous acoustic signal, these instructions are abstract discrete logical entities. As such they are more robust and stable than the malleable continuous objects that make up acoustic signals. Hence, rather than a small quantitative error, a large qualitative error would have to be made in order to mutate the rhythm.

- This type of evolution is called Weismannian evolution.
- In recent years, much research has been done to uncover the fascinating relationships between music and language. It is therefore not surprising that many cultures have passed on rhythms from one generation to another by means of mnemonics.
- Safi al-Din's book appears to contain the earliest historical records of the clave son rhythm. Written notations such as these are examples of sets of instructions that provide an even higher copying-fidelity than mnemonic syllable systems, and therefore they greatly facilitate Weismannian evolution.
- Experiments by Stephen Handel demonstrated that "Two rhythms that had the same perceptual grouping were judged as being identical, even if the timing between the groups was different.
- It is easier for subjects to judge whether an inter-onset interval duration is equal to, greater than, or less than, the preceding or the following duration, than to judge quantitative relations such as twice as long or half as long.
- However, the fact that the clave son existed in Baghdad hundreds of years before the slave migrations from West Africa to the New World, and that in the West African oral musical tradition rhythms were coded mnemonically, suggests that both the binary and ternary versions of the clave son probably existed simultaneously in West Africa before the advent of the slave trade, and that they migrated independently to the New World.
- The clave son rhythmic pattern acquired its name from the type of Cuban music known as the son. The cradle of the son music is the eastern Cuban province of Oriente, where it may have taken preliminary forms in the seventeenth century. However, in several accounts, its verified existence comes later, in the nineteenth century in the cities of Guantánamo, Baracoa, Manzanillo, and Santiago de Cuba, where it took on its more present-day form in the early twentieth century.
- Rhythm timelines are a type of cultural object. A rhythm that is considered successful from an evolutionary perspective will survive and multiply.
- The power of a rhythm timeline to disseminate itself among different cultural communities is the property of fecundity.
- Abundant evidence has been put forward that the clave son is such a rhythm, and thus it is only fitting that it should be investigated to determine the musicological and mathematical reasons for its fertility.

Appendix B: Resources

The R Project for Statistical Computing:

<https://www.r-project.org>

Package multicool:

<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/multicool/index.html>

Ableton Live set with Interval Combinatorial Classes:

https://www.dropbox.com/s/2ux0khx2jx0apfm/combinatorics_classes_R_Final%20Project.zip?dl=0

Online Evaluation Survey:

http://www.dtic.upf.edu/~conuanain/chai_survey/start.php

